

Taxonomic Reassessment of the Nearctic Mantodea with New Regional Records

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Abstract. Updated synthesis of Nearctic Mantodea, presenting revised key to all established genera in the U.S. and Canada and incorporating major recent taxonomic treatments. New distributional data include: first documentation of *Iris oratoria* in Mexico, continued spread of *Miomantis caffra* in California and widespread continental expansion of *Mantis religiosa* into Canada and Mexico. Updated *Stagmomantis* treatments record multiple new localities and confirm established *Stagmomantis montana* population in Florida. The rapid expansion of *Statilia maculata* is documented, along with newly detected U.S. occurrences of *Hierodula*, *Rivetina*, *Sphodromantis* and additional non-native *Stagmomantis* and *Tenodera* species. Discussion of heterospecific mate attraction summarizes recent field observations that demonstrate cross-species mounting and attempted copulation events within Mantidae.

Anderson's *Praying Mantises of the United States and Canada* (2018, 1st Edition; 2019, 2nd Edition) established a comprehensive synthesis of all known Mantodea species occurring within the Nearctic region at the time. This foundational work consolidated over two centuries of scattered literature and historical field observations into a modernized treatment of the Nearctic fauna. Since the publication of this text, several taxonomic revisions by the present author have further refined our understanding of the relationships, boundaries, and diagnostic features among Nearctic mantises. At the same time, rapidly accumulating distributional data have documented both previously unrecognized native ranges and multiple adventive populations introduced through commerce, horticulture, and the pet trade. The purpose of this contribution is to bring these disparate developments together as a concise taxonomic reassessment of the Nearctic Mantodea, providing updated nomenclature, revised species delimitations, new or expanded dichotomous keys, and a curated list of notable new regional records at the country, state, province, and county levels. In addition, this supplement includes a dedicated section on heterospecific mate attraction, summarizing field observations and behavioral analyses that reveal cross-species mounting and attempted copulation events among adventive and native taxa. This section contextualizes these interactions within the broader reproductive ecology of Mantodea and provides new insight into lineage-specific mate-recognition thresholds in the Nearctic fauna.

This contribution recognizes the increasing role of digital platforms in documenting mantis biodiversity. Of particular importance is iNaturalist.org, an open-access, community-driven database where users—ranging from amateur naturalists to professional taxonomists—upload georeferenced photographs and field observations that undergo expert review. These vetted observations have become indispensable for tracking range expansions, recognizing incipient adventive populations, and identifying outlying

records that would rarely be detected through traditional collecting alone. In many cases, iNaturalist data now provide the earliest evidence of establishment for non-native species and the first provincial or state records for poorly sampled native taxa, thereby complementing and extending museum-based knowledge. Notably, the entirety of heterospecific mating events documented in this supplement were detected solely through such community-science platforms, highlighting their growing relevance not only for distributional research but also for ethological inquiry.

The rapid growth of citizen science initiatives such as iNaturalist has transformed the documentation of Nearctic Mantodea. Many recent distributional confirmations and adventive species detections have originated from observations made by non-specialists equipped with high-resolution smartphone cameras and an enthusiasm for contributing to biodiversity knowledge. This collaboration between the public and professional researchers has markedly increased both the frequency and geographic breadth of mantis records across North America. Accordingly, this contribution not only reflects taxonomic advancements since 2019 but also acknowledges the indispensable role of community science in modern entomological research. By merging the findings of rigorous taxonomic revisions with new distribution range data with ethological observations generated by citizen scientists, this work provides an expanded and contemporary framework for understanding the dynamic, evolving distribution and ecology of Mantodea in the United States and Canada.

Key to the Mantodea Genera of the United States and Canada:

- 1 Head capsule without ocellar process 2
- 1' Head capsule bearing pair of distinct, horn-like ocellar processes *Pseudovates*

- 2 Antennae thin, filiform 3
- 2' Antennae thick, especially at base *Brunneria*

- 3 Compound eyes rounded or weakly conical with blunt points. Metathoracic femora of normal proportions to mesothoracic femora in length. Wings present in males 4
- 3' Compound eyes strongly conical with acute points. Metathoracic femora greatly elongated, measuring nearly twice as long as mesothoracic femora, giving mantis a grasshopper-like appearance. Males wingless *Yersiniops*

- 4 Pronotum elongated, measuring several times longer than wide 5
- 4' Pronotum squarish, measuring about as long as wide *Mantoida*

- 5 Habitus dorsoventrally flattened. Occurs on tree trunks, strictly bark-dwelling 6
- 5' Habitus more proportionate, not flattened. Occurs in a variety of terrestrial and vegetation habitats 7

- 6 Discoidal spines of forefemora arranged in zigzag pattern. Metasternum without auditory organ, earless. Supra-anal plate round *Liturgusa*
- 6' Discoidal spines of forefemora arranged in straight line. Metasternum bearing auditory organ. Supra-anal plate triangular *Gonatista*

- 7 Foretibiae bearing 1-4 (occasionally 5) ventral spines and at least one dorsal spine. Head with very prominent juxtaocular bulges 8
- 7' Foretibiae bearing more than 4 ventral spines and no dorsal spine. Head with inconspicuous juxtaocular bulges 10

- 8 Metazona measures at most two times as long as prozona. Forefemora with 4 discoidal spines; foretibiae with 1 dorsal spine 9
- 8' Metazona measures three times as long as prozona. Forefemora with 3 discoidal spines; foretibiae with 2 dorsal spines *Thesprotia*
- 9 Pronotum elongated, metazona measuring twice as long as prozona. Supracoxal dilation placed in anterior third of pronotum, lobes angular *Bistanta*
- 9' Pronotum short and thickset, metazona measuring just slightly longer than prozona. Supracoxal dilation placed slightly forward of middle of pronotum, lobes rounded *Thespis*
- 10 Posteroventral spines of foretibiae straight, spaced apart, erect to oblique 11
- 10' Posteroventral spines of foretibiae curved, placed close together, recumbent *Acontista*
- 11 Foretibiae measure significantly more than one-half the length of forefemora. Internal surface of forefemora either monochromatic or with small, darkened blotches near base of spines and tibial spur groove, devoid of large, colorful blotches 12
- 11' Foretibiae measure less than one-half as long as forefemora. Internal surface of forefemora colorfully marked with black, white and reddish blotches *Statilia*
- 12 Pronotum measures significantly longer than forecoxae. Habitus small to large, predominantly pigmented in greens with some individuals being brownish or gray. Primarily found among vegetation 13
- 12' Pronotum measures only slightly longer than forecoxae. Habitus small, consistently pigmented in browns and grays, never green. Primarily ground-dwelling *Litaneutria*
- 13 Lower frons smooth or with low carinae. Forefemora with 4 posteroventral spines. Anal area of hindwings tessellate, uniformly mottled, monochromatic, or hyaline 14
- 13' Lower frons with pair of tubercles. Forefemora with 5 posteroventral spines. Anal area of hindwings with large, shiny, bluish-black blotch amidst yellowish field *Iris*
- 14 Lower frons spanning less than or just equal to twice as wide as high. Female forewings reaching at least to tip of abdomen 16
- 14' Lower frons spanning significantly more than twice as wide as high. Female forewings shorter than abdomen 15
- 15 Tibial spur groove placed in proximal half of forefemora. Foretibiae with 6-7 posteroventral and 9 anteroventral spines *Miomantis*
- 15' Tibial spur groove placed in distal half, almost in middle, of forefemora. Foretibiae with 8-11 posteroventral and 11-17 anteroventral spines *Stagmomantis*
- 16 Interior base of forecoxae immaculate. Hindwings lightly infumate to heavily maculated *Tenodera*
- 16' Interior base of forecoxae bearing a large, circular spot. Hindwings entirely hyaline *Mantis*

Acontista Saussure & Zehntner, 1894

Species Checklist of the United States & Canada:

- *Acontista cordillerae* Saussure, 1869

Remarks. Since the account of initial occurrence published by Anderson (2021), this species has been repeatedly documented in southern Florida, confirming its continued presence and establishment in the

region. The Palm Beach/Broward County population has now been reconfirmed by multiple subsequent observations from surrounding parklands. These records include both nymphs and adult females, demonstrating multigenerational persistence and stable annual recurrence at the original locality. The new records indicate that the species is now well established in Palm Beach County. Although an introduction via imported Neotropical plants remains a plausible explanation, particularly given the proximity of the original occurrence sites to botanical and horticultural facilities, the possibility that *cordillerae* represents a cryptic native component of the southern Florida Mantodea fauna cannot be discounted. The species occurs across a broad range from Mexico and Central America into northwestern South America, and its established presence in Florida may reflect a naturally occurring but historically undetected northernmost population at very low density. The rediscovery of the species across several years, coupled with its localized but persistent distribution, lends credence to both hypotheses. Regardless of its origin, *cordillerae* is now recognized as a member of the established North American fauna. Its confirmed populations in Palm Beach and Broward counties represent the northernmost documented occurrences of *Acontista* in the Western Hemisphere. Continued monitoring is warranted to determine whether the species will further expand its range within peninsular Florida or remain restricted to the current cluster of low-density, localized populations.

Bistanta Anderson, 2018

Species Checklist of the United States & Canada:

- Bistanta campestris* Anderson, 2022
- Bistanta herema* Anderson, 2022

Key to *Bistanta* Males of the United States & Canada:

- 1 Forewings measuring 2.3-2.4 times longer than pronotal length, entirely hyaline, apices clear. Supraanal plate measuring 1.24 times longer than basal width. Occurs in the Sonoran Desert *B. herema*
- 1' Forewings measuring 2.0-2.1 times longer than pronotal length, lightly to moderately tessellate with light brown, apices darkened. Supraanal plate measuring 1.55 times longer than basal width. Occurs in Tamaulipas-Texas plain *B. campestris*

Key to *Bistanta* Females of the United States & Canada:

- 1 Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width >7.0, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width >9.0, supracoxal dilation width to minimal metazonal width <1.2 *B. campestris*
- 1' Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width <7.0, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width <9.0, supracoxal dilation width to minimal metazonal width >1.2 *B. herema*

Remarks. *Bistanta mexicana* (Saussure & Zehntner, 1894) was historically regarded as a broadly distributed species ranging from the Pacific lowlands of Mexico northward into the southwestern United States. However, recent analysis from Anderson (2022a) has shown that *Bistanta* is entirely absent from the Chihuahuan Desert, a biogeographical barrier that effectively separates the Sonoran and Tamaulipas–Texas faunal regions. According to current understanding, *mexicana* is confined to the Pacific coastal plain of western Mexico, particularly west of the Sierra Madre Occidental. It inhabits coastal lowlands of Sinaloa and adjacent regions, but does not occur in the arid habitats of northern Sonora or east of the Sierra Madre Occidental. Populations previously attributed to *mexicana* from Arizona and Texas represent distinct taxa: *herema* in Arizona and *campestris* in Texas. These two lineages exhibit clear morphological differentiation from *mexicana* and from one another, reflecting long-term geographic isolation. Consequently, *mexicana* is regarded as endemic to western Mexico and excluded from the fauna of the United States.

Brunneria Saussure, 1869

Species Checklist of the United States & Canada:

•*Brunneria borealis* Scudder, 1896

Remarks. Cabe et al. (2024) provided the first genetic comparison between *borealis* and its South American congener *Brunneria subaptera* Saussure, 1869, revealing that the single mitochondrial COI haplotype found throughout the broad North American range of *borealis* falls entirely within the genetic variation of *subaptera* populations from Uruguay. This striking genetic similarity, combined with the absence of intraspecific variation among North American specimens, strongly suggests that *borealis* represents a relatively recent introduction of *subaptera* into the United States, rather than a native Nearctic lineage. The authors proposed that this introduction likely resulted from transport of an ootheca or adult female from South America, and they recommended that, under the principle of priority, the name *subaptera* may ultimately apply to all populations once the genus is comprehensively reviewed. However, Cabe et al. exercised appropriate caution and did not formally synonymize the two species, noting that *Brunneria* as a whole requires a detailed revision incorporating broader genetic and morphological datasets before any nomenclatural changes are made. The mitochondrial marker employed in their study is well suited for assessing population-level structure and provides a robust indication of close genetic relatedness, yet it does not by itself resolve species boundaries. At present, *borealis* is best regarded as an introduced derivative of *subaptera* that has been established within the southeastern United States. The historical pathway of its introduction remains unknown. A comprehensive revision of *Brunneria* is both feasible and necessary to clarify the relationships among its described species and to determine whether *borealis* should indeed be subsumed under *subaptera*. Pending such a review, synonymy is not recommended and *borealis* is provisionally retained as a valid species. The distribution of this species remains largely consistent with that presented in Anderson's 2019 text, which documented the species as a specialist of the southeastern United States. No major westward or northward expansions have been detected since that publication. However, a noteworthy and naturally occurring range extension into extreme southeastern Virginia has been confirmed through multiple independent photographic records posted to iNaturalist. These occurrences represent the first verified country- and county-equivalent jurisdiction records for Virginia. The species' arrival in this region is biologically plausible given the contiguity of suitable Atlantic Coastal Plain habitat extending northward from North Carolina. At present, the Virginia records appear to reflect a genuine but limited natural expansion rather than anthropogenic introduction. Continued monitoring will determine whether *borealis* becomes more broadly established within the Virginia Tidewater region.

United States

Virginia

- Langley AFB, City of Hampton, VA – adult female (08.30.19) Observation ID: 31794467
- Willoughby Spit, City of Norfolk, VA – adult female (09.01.19) Observation ID: 31963469
- Virginia Beach, City of Virginia Beach, VA – nymph (07.29.23) Observation ID: 175626680
- Yorktown, York Co, VA – adult female (10.04.21) Observation ID: 97177182

Gonatista Saussure, 1869

Species Checklist of the United States & Canada:

•*Gonatista bifasciata* (de Haan, 1842)

Remarks. *Gonatista grisea* (Fabricius, 1793) held long-standing usage to refer to the species of *Gonatista* that encompasses the widespread Caribbean and southeastern North American taxon. Anderson (2025: 47) re-examined the type basis and diagnostic elements associated with *grisea* and demonstrated that the description and cited locality data are insufficient to establish its identity with certainty. As a result, the name was rendered *nomen dubium*. In accordance with the Principle of Priority and the need for

nomenclatural stability, *Mantis bifasciata* de Haan, 1842—previously regarded as a junior synonym of *grisea*—was reinstated as the valid name for this well-defined species. The present work follows that treatment, recognizing the species as *Gonatista bifasciata* (de Haan, 1842). In Anderson’s 2019 text, this species was hypothesized to occur continuously, though sparsely, across the Gulf Coast region from Florida westward to Texas. This projected distribution reflected both the species’ ecological affinity for humid subtropical coastal habitats and the absence of clear biogeographical barriers separating the two previously known population centers. At that time, however, only direct confirmation of *bifasciata* occurring in Alabama was available. Subsequent iNaturalist records now substantiate this earlier prediction. Verified occurrences from Louisiana and Mississippi demonstrate that *bifasciata* does indeed inhabit the intervening Gulf Coast corridor. These detections remain few in number but they conclusively validate the species’ continuous presence across the region. All current evidence supports a stable but under-detected distribution spanning the full breadth of the U.S. Gulf Coast.

United States

Alabama

- Kinsey, Houston Co, AL – adult female (12.06.19) Observation ID: 36411547

Louisiana

- Covington, St. Tammany Parish, LA – adult male (10.27.25) Observation ID: 323445185

Mississippi

- Gautier, Jackson Co, MS – adult female (10.10.24) Observation ID: 246670127

Iris Saussure, 1869

Species Checklist of the United States & Canada:

- *Iris oratoria* (Linné, 1758)

Remarks. Three records of *oratoria* from Alabama, Illinois, and West Virginia fall well outside the known Nearctic distribution of this Mediterranean-adapted species, which is firmly established only in the arid and semi-arid regions of the southwestern United States (California, Nevada, Utah, Arizona, New Mexico, and Texas). These peripheral detections represent isolated adventive occurrences rather than evidence of natural range expansion or local establishment.

United States

Alabama

- Georgiana, Butler County, AL – adult male (04.30.19) Observation ID: 25095951

Illinois

- Vandalia, Fayette County, IL – nymph (07.21.24) Observation ID: 230858507

West Virginia

- Charleston, Kanawha County, WV – adult female (10.22.18) Observation ID: 17749704

The Illinois record (Fayette County) is particularly instructive. The specimen was a solitary nymph photographed while perched on the tread of a large truck tire—a context strongly indicative of accidental inland transport via commercial cargo rather than local origin. Central Illinois possesses a humid continental climate characterized by cold winters, high precipitation, and mesic deciduous forest ecosystems, all of which are incompatible with the physiological and reproductive requirements of *oratoria*, a species adapted to Mediterranean climates with mild winters and prolonged warm, dry seasons. No adults, oothecae, or subsequent generations have been recorded from Illinois or elsewhere in the Midwest, and there is no evidence of reproduction, persistence, or incipient establishment. This event is most plausibly interpreted as a single, non-establishing adventive introduction facilitated by vehicular transport from a region where the species is well established. The West Virginia record (Kanawha County) raises similar concerns. Like Illinois, West Virginia’s climate and vegetation structure are inconsistent with the species’ environmental tolerances. The context of the observation suggests that this individual may have been inadvertently introduced through ornamental plantings or garden materials rather than representing a naturally occurring or persistent population. As with the Illinois specimen, no

additional records from any life stage have been documented, and no evidence suggests the presence of a resident population. The Alabama record (Butler County) is likewise considered dubious from an establishment standpoint. Although Alabama's climate is comparatively milder, it still lacks the characteristic Mediterranean regime to which *oratoria* is evolutionarily adapted. With only a single adult male documented and no corroborating observations of oothecae, nymphs, or subsequent generations, the event is best explained as another isolated, adventive introduction. Taken together, these three records do not alter the known distribution of *oratoria* in North America. Rather, they reflect sporadic, non-establishing introductions likely mediated by human transport of cargo, vehicles, or ornamental plants. In contrast to these isolated adventive occurrences in the United States, what has not been thoroughly documented until now is the widespread and well-established presence of *oratoria* throughout northern and central Mexico. Although this species has been recognized in California since its mid-20th century introduction, its occurrence across Mexico has remained largely unreported in the formal literature. The records listed below represent only the first confirmed state-level occurrences for Mexico, yet they dramatically understate the true scale of the species' distribution. At present, several hundred additional observations of *oratoria* from across Mexico appear on iNaturalist.org, collectively demonstrating that the species is thoroughly established throughout the northern tier of the country—regions that share nearly identical climatic and ecological conditions with the southwestern United States where the species is long naturalized.

Mexico

- Tijuana, Baja California, Mexico – adult male (09.02.08) Observation ID: 251986508
- Delicias, Chihuahua, Mexico – adult female (09.27.12) Observation ID: 96980982
- Torreón, Coahuila de Zaragoza, Mexico – adult female (01.09.11) Observation ID: 5186274
- Lerdo, Durango, Mexico – adult male (07.24.19) Observation ID: 29484461
- Acámbaro, Guanajuato, Mexico – adult female (08.25.19) Observation ID: 118705609
- Tixtla de Guerrero, Guerrero, Mexico – ootheca (04.23.22) Observation ID: 117737216
- San Bartolo Tutotepec, Hidalgo, Mexico – adult female (10.06.21) Observation ID: 97387181
- Mazatlán, Sinaloa, Mexico – ootheca (07.12.16) Observation ID: 3670212
- Hermosillo, Sonora, Mexico – adult male (01.13.02) Observation ID: 12212183
- Tlaxcala, Tlaxcala, Mexico – nymph (09.13.16) Observation ID: 4104230

Importantly, the earliest of these verified Mexican records dates to 2002 (Hermosillo, Sonora), indicating that *oratoria* has been present in Mexico for at least two decades, and likely considerably longer. The wide geographic spread of these first-state records, from Baja California and Sonora in the northwest to Guerrero, Puebla-adjacent Tlaxcala, and Hidalgo in central Mexico, demonstrates that this species occupies both arid and semi-arid habitats as well as transitional highland environments. This broad ecological tolerance parallels its Nearctic behavior and further supports its long-term establishment across the Mexican landscape. Despite the species' prolific spread within Mexico, its presence there has not been addressed in formal research, making the present documentation the first consolidated summary of its Mexican distribution. These findings underscore the scientific value of iNaturalist, which continues to reveal previously undocumented biogeographic patterns, including extensive, well-established non-native distributions that traditional literature has yet to record.

Litaneutria Saussure, 1892

Species Checklist of the United States & Canada:

- *Litaneutria baccina* Anderson, 2021
- *Litaneutria chaparrali* Anderson, 2021
- *Litaneutria emarginata* Anderson, 2018
- *Litaneutria minor* (Scudder, 1872)
- *Litaneutria obscura* Scudder, 1896
- *Litaneutria ocularis* Saussure, 1892
- *Litaneutria pacifica* Scudder, 1896

- Litaneutria scopulosa* Anderson, 2021
- Litaneutria skinneri* Rehn, 1907
- Litaneutria superna* Anderson, 2021

Key to *Litaneutria* Males of the United States & Canada:

- | | | |
|----|---|----------------------|
| 1 | Middle of vertex level with or arched above dorsal surface of compound eyes | 2 |
| 1' | Middle of vertex placed below dorsal surface of compound eyes | 3 |
| 2 | Pronotum slender; pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.46, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.83. Brachypterous individuals co-occur with macropterous forms ... <i>L. skinneri</i> | |
| 2' | Pronotum subcompact; pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.13, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.40. Solely brachypterous | <i>L. baccina</i> |
| 3 | Dorsal surface of compound eyes bluntly conical | 4 |
| 3' | Dorsal surface of compound eyes truncated to rounded | 5 |
| 4 | Supracoxal dilation pronounced; pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.41, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.69. Precinctive to Southern California Chaparral | <i>L. chaparrali</i> |
| 4' | Supracoxal dilation moderately marked; pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.66, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.80. Precinctive to Southern Texas Plains | <i>L. emarginata</i> |
| 5 | Brachypterous—wings shortened as in female | 11 |
| 5' | Macropterous—wings fully lengthened | 6 |
| 6 | Anal area of hindwings with light to very dark maculation. Hindwing spot light to heavily darkened, always present. Occurs in various mountainous, xeric and grassland regions east to north of Sierra Nevada | 7 |
| 6' | Anal area of hindwings with faint maculation. Hindwing spot faint, occasionally absent. Precinctive to Mediterranean California | <i>L. pacifica</i> |
| 7 | Hindwing maculation light to moderate, light brownish in coloration. Delimitation of hindwing spot clearly defined, contrasted against lighter surrounding maculation | 8 |
| 7' | Hindwing maculation typically heavy, dark brown to blackish in coloration. Delimitation of hindwing spot poorly defined, obscured against dark surrounding maculation | <i>L. obscura</i> |
| 8 | Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width <2.36, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width <3.49. Occurs in high elevation mountainous regions | 9 |
| 8' | Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width >2.36, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width >3.49. Occurs in low elevation xeric and grassland regions | 10 |
| 9 | Hindwings short and narrow. Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.35, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.37. Precinctive to Columbia Plateau/Blue Mountain foothills and adjacent Okanogan Plateau within Cascadia | <i>L. superna</i> |
| 9' | Hindwings long and narrow. Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.27, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.47. Precinctive to Colorado Plateau and Southern Rockies within Rocky Mountains, extending marginally into the adjacent northern Sonoran Desert of central Arizona | <i>L. scopulosa</i> |

- 10 Compound eyes narrowly ovoid, somewhat truncated. Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.48, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.50. Precinctive to Chihuahuan Desert and Great Plains *L. minor*
- 10' Compound eyes prominently rounded. Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.37, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.53. Precinctive to Sonoran and Baja California Deserts *L. ocularis*
- 11 Pronotal length to minimal metazonal width <3.65. Occurs east or north of Sierra Nevada 12
- 11' Pronotal length to minimal metazonal width >3.65. Occurs west of Sierra Nevada *L. pacifica*
- 12 Pronotum shortened, relatively robust; pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.27-2.35. Occurs in high elevation xeric regions west of or within the Rocky Mountains 13
- 12' Pronotum elongated; pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.48. Precinctive to Chihuahuan Desert and Great Plains *L. minor*
- 13 Compound eyes prominently rounded. Occurs south to southeast of Cascadia 14
- 13' Compound eyes narrowly ovoid. Precinctive to Columbia Plateau/Blue Mountain foothills and adjacent Okanogan Plateau within Cascadia *L. superna*
- 14 Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.27. Pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.47. Precinctive to Colorado Plateau and Southern Rockies, extending marginally into the adjacent northern Sonoran Desert of central Arizona *L. scopulosa*
- 14' Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.34. Pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.54. Precinctive to Mojave Desert *L. obscura*

Key to *Litaneutria* Females of the United States & Canada:

- 1 Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width >2, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width >3 2
- 1' Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width <2, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width <3 *L. baccina*
- 2 Occurs in coastal, high elevation cold desert, or low elevation warm desert regions west of or within the Rocky Mountains 4
- 2' Occurs in grassland and low elevation xeric regions east or south of the Rocky Mountains 3
- 3 Vertex placed significantly lower than dorsal surface of compound eyes, bearing deep sulcus in middle. Compound eyes weakly conical, dorsal surface raised into blunted points .. *L. emarginata*
- 3' Vertex slightly raised above dorsal surface of compound eyes with middle portion smoothed into shallow arch. Compound eyes narrowly rounded, dorsal surface somewhat truncated *L. minor*
- 4 Dorsal surface of compound eyes broadly rounded. Occurs east or north of the Sierra Nevada ... 6
- 4' Dorsal surface of compound eyes narrowly rounded to sharply angulate. Occurs west or south of the Sierra Nevada 5
- 5 Vertex slightly raised above dorsal surface of compound eyes, flattened to weakly convex in middle. Dorsal surface of compound eyes sharply angulate *L. chaparrali*
- 5' Vertex raised well above dorsal surface of compound eyes, broadly arched in middle. Dorsal surface of compound eyes narrowly rounded *L. pacifica*
- 6 Vertex level with or raised slightly above dorsal surface of compound eyes in shallow arch. Compound eyes protruding 7

- 6' Vertex raised in high arch above dorsal surface of compound eyes. Compound eyes narrowly ovoid *L. skinneri*
- 7 Pronotal length to minimal metazonal width <3.16. Occurs in cold desert regions 8
- 7' Pronotal length to minimal metazonal width >3.21. Occurs in warm desert regions 9
- 8 Supracoxal dilation narrow, indistinct; pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.30. Precinctive to Columbia Plateau/Blue Mountain foothills and adjacent Okanogan Plateau within Cascadia *L. superna*
- 8' Supracoxal dilation broad, pronounced; pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.17. Precinctive to Colorado Plateau and Southern Rockies within Rocky Mountains, extending marginally into the adjacent northern Sonoran Desert of central Arizona *L. scopulosa*
- 9 Pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.41. Precinctive to Mojave Desert *L. obscura*
- 9' Pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.21. Precinctive to Sonoran Desert *L. ocularis*

Remarks. The genus *Litaneutria* was substantially revised by Anderson (2021a), who redefined the limits of the Nearctic taxa and reassessed the historical nomenclature associated with the group. Prior to this revision, six species were recognized in the 2019 edition of *Praying Mantises of the United States and Canada*. Anderson confirmed that earlier treatments had conflated several morphologically distinct lineages. The genus is now understood to comprise eleven valid species occurring within North America. This revision resulted in the reinstatement of *obscura* to full species status and *elongata* Anderson, 2018 was placed in synonymy with *ocularis*. Five additional species were newly described: *baccina*, *chaparrali*, *scopulosa*, *superna* from the United States and *littoralis* from Mexico. This arrangement replaces the six-species framework previously recognized in the 2019 text and represents the current taxonomic treatment adopted herein.

Liturgusa Saussure, 1869

Species Checklist of the United States & Canada:

- *Liturgusa maya* (Saussure & Zehntner, 1894)

Remarks. Since the account published in Anderson's 2018 first edition, documentation of *maya* within Florida has expanded only minimally. A single verified observation from Monroe County represents the only new locality record since the establishment of a stable, parthenogenetically reproducing colony in Broward County first recognized in 2013. This county record confirms that the species occurs at least sporadically outside Broward County; however, no additional spread has been detected in the intervening years.

United States

Florida

- Florida Bay, Monroe Co, FL – nymph (07.03.22) Observation ID: 141041999

This limited expansion is notable given that the surrounding region of southern Florida, particularly Miami-Dade and Palm Beach counties, possesses ecological conditions nearly identical to Broward County and would be expected to be highly suitable for *maya*. Despite this, thousands of reports of other mantis species from these adjacent counties have accumulated on the iNaturalist platform without yielding further *maya* detections. This absence of new records may reflect one or more factors: (1) the species' secretive, bark-dwelling habits, which reduce detection probability; (2) the possibility that the Broward County population remains geographically constrained; or (3) the potential for past collapses and recolonizations, consistent with the species' facultative parthenogenesis and its reliance on periodic male reintroduction to sustain long-term population viability. To date, all confirmed specimens from Florida continue to be female, and no evidence has yet emerged of established male presence within the U.S.

population. This demographic pattern is fully consistent with the 2018 interpretation that the Broward County colony may be repeatedly founded through independent introductions, potentially linked to commercial pathways involving Neotropical plant or fauna imports. The lack of significant post-2018 expansion, even into ecologically contiguous regions, suggests that *maya* remains locally established but not widely invasive within the United States. Continued monitoring is advisable, as the species' cryptic behavior and parthenogenetic capability leave open the possibility of future detections beyond its presently confirmed range.

Mantis Linné, 1758

Species Checklist of the United States & Canada:

• *Mantis religiosa* Linné, 1758

Remarks. Since the publication of Anderson's 2019 second edition, this species has continued to expand its presence across the United States, with several new state-level occurrences documented here for the first time. Although this species is one of the most frequently reintroduced mantises in North America, it remains limited in its ability to establish stable, reproducing populations outside of its core temperate range. As Anderson (2019: 3) previously noted, oothecae of *religiosa* are widely sold through plant nurseries, garden centers, and online vendors under the false premise that mantises serve as effective biological control agents. This misguided propagation results in *religiosa* appearing virtually anywhere in the continental United States, but these occurrences seldom translate into long-term establishment. The species' Nearctic distribution remains closely tied to regions exhibiting temperate, seasonal climates with sufficiently cold winters and mesic vegetation communities, broadly corresponding to the western United States and the New England region. This species continues to demonstrate difficulty establishing within the southern United States, even as isolated adventive specimens, due to climatic incompatibility. Thus, despite substantial repeated anthropogenic introductions, stable populations remain largely absent across the Southeast. Nevertheless, *religiosa* continues to expand into the interior states where climate and habitat conditions more closely resemble its established western and northeastern ranges. The new state records presented here represent only the earliest documented occurrences within each state; many of these states now possess multiple counties with subsequent sightings, reflecting ongoing dispersal and localized establishment.

United States

Florida

- Tampa, Hillsborough County, FL – adult female (10.18.18) Observation ID: 17649407

Iowa

- Sioux Center, Sioux County, IA – adult male (08.01.21) Observation ID: 91217318

Kentucky

- Bowling Green, Warren County, KY – adult female (12.07.17) Observation ID: 9083333

Minnesota

- Chaska, Carver County, MN – adult female (08.27.21) Observation ID: 92708724

Mississippi

- Long Beach, Harrison County, MS – adult female (10.21.25) Observation ID: 322313144

Missouri

- Polo, Caldwell County, MO – adult female (09.11.19) Observation ID: 32621951

North Carolina

- Greensboro, Guilford County, NC – adult female (10.08.23) Observation ID: 187187576

Oklahoma

- McCurtain County, OK – adult female (02.04.11) Observation ID: 15009961

South Carolina

- Greenville County, SC – adult male (07.01.18) Observation ID: 15595670

Tennessee

- Manchester, Coffee County, TN – adult female (09.26.20) Observation ID: 61170085

Texas

- Austin, Burnet County, TX – adult female (09.05.19) Observation ID: 32190949

This species has also demonstrated continued expansion into both Canada and Mexico since the 2019 publication. The provincial and state records listed below represent the first documented occurrences within those respective jurisdictions; however, they do not reflect the full extent of the species' presence. Each of these provinces and states now has multiple subsequent observations, confirming that *religiosa* is locally established or at least repeatedly detected well beyond the initial discovery event. In Canada, *religiosa* has long been established in southern Ontario and Québec, yet the species is now appearing far outside this traditional core range. Verified first occurrences in Alberta, Manitoba, New Brunswick, Nova Scotia, and Saskatchewan demonstrate a notable expansion westward and eastward into temperate, often prairie or maritime regions. This pattern is consistent with the species' ecological preferences for cooler temperate climates and mirrors the expansion dynamics previously documented in the northern United States. Many of these Canadian provinces now possess multiple records, confirming that the species is not merely introduced sporadically, but is recurrently present across broad geographic areas.

Canada

- Calgary, Alberta, Canada – adult female (09.03.20) Observation ID: 59190305
- Winnipeg, Manitoba, Canada – adult female (08.20.21) Observation ID: 91845171
- Moncton, New Brunswick, Canada – adult female (11.04.22) Observation ID: 141482695
- Hants, Nova Scotia, Canada – adult female (09.05.18) Observation ID: 16265690
- Val Marie, Saskatchewan, Canada – adult male (09.20.25) Observation ID: 320188883

In Mexico, the presence of *religiosa* has historically been under-documented. Hernández-Baltazar & Gómez (2017: 176) reported *religiosa* only from Coahuila and Tamaulipas, marking the first formal documentation of the species in Mexico. Since that publication, however, additional observations have accumulated from Baja California, Ciudad de México and Nuevo León, as reflected in the first-occurrence records listed here. These records reveal a more complex and geographically extensive Mexican distribution than previously recognized. As with the Canadian material, these occurrences represent only the initial verified detections. The growing corpus of Mexican records strongly suggests that *religiosa* is expanding southward into the xeric and temperate highland regions of northern and central Mexico, environments broadly comparable to the southwestern United States where the species is well established. Whether these Mexican populations derive from natural dispersal from U.S. populations, from independent anthropogenic introductions, or from multiple sources remains uncertain. Regardless, the expanding distribution demonstrates that *religiosa* is now a widespread element of the North American mantis fauna extending from Canada to central Mexico. As with the other species treated in this supplement, these findings underscore the critical role of platforms such as iNaturalist in documenting ongoing distributional changes, particularly for cosmopolitan or frequently introduced mantises whose Nearctic ranges remain dynamic and incompletely understood.

Mexico

- Tecate, Baja California, Mexico – adult female (09.20.24) Observation ID: 242943349
- Xochimilco, Ciudad de México, Mexico – adult female (01.07.25) Observation ID: 257680309
- Santa Catarina, Nuevo León, Mexico – adult female (04.25.25) Observation ID: 273329321

The expanding geographic footprint of *religiosa* across the United States, Canada, and Mexico underscores this species' capacity to persist in a broad spectrum of environments. Equally informative, are the species' foraging behaviors, which illuminate how *religiosa* confronts and overcomes ecological challenges within these newly occupied habitats. Among the most illustrative of these behaviors is its handling of toxic prey, a scenario that demonstrates the species' behavioral flexibility in exploiting chemically defended insects. Praying mantises encountering toxic insects often employ a distinctive prey-processing technique in which the predator pierces the integument, extracts the gut contents, and discards the unsavory slurry before consuming the remaining tissues. This behavior, termed "gutting," was first formally documented for *Tenodera sinensis* by Rafter et al. (2013), who demonstrated that this species consistently removed the gut of *Danaus plexippus* larvae while wholly consuming non-toxic

lepidopteran prey. Consistent with these documented observations of *sinensis*, an adult female *religiosa* was recently observed exhibiting the same behavior—opening the integument of a late-instar monarch larva, allowing the green vegetal mass of the gut to fall free, and consuming only the remaining tissues.

01, *Mantis religiosa* gutting behavior. Castaic, Los Angeles Co, CA 08.07.25 (Photo: Avery Hansen)

Mantoida Newman, 1838

Species Checklist of the United States & Canada:

- *Mantoida maya* Saussure & Zehntner, 1894

Miomantis Saussure, 1870

Species Checklist of the United States & Canada:

- *Miomantis caffra* Saussure, 1871

Remarks. Since the initial documentation of this species in Anderson’s 2018 first edition, *caffra* has undergone significant expansion within California, particularly throughout the Los Angeles Basin and into the greater San Diego region. The original records documented the presence of a well-established reproductive colony in Los Angeles and Orange counties. Since that publication, verified observations have expanded markedly. New county records now include Alameda County (Hayward), Contra Costa

County (Tara Hills), San Diego County (San Diego), and San Joaquin County (Stockton). These records represent only the first documented occurrences for each county. They do not reflect the true volume of observations, which now number in the hundreds across Los Angeles and San Diego counties alone, supported by repeated annual detections of adults, nymphs, and oothecae in residential neighborhoods, landscaped environments, and urban green spaces.

United States

California

- Hayward, Alameda Co, CA – adult female (11.30.18) Observation ID: 47923898
- Tara Hills, Contra Costa Co, CA – nymph (09.22.24) Observation ID: 243525323
- San Diego, San Diego Co, CA – nymph (06.07.19) Observation ID: 26565497
- Stockton, San Joaquin Co, CA – adult female (05.06.18) Observation ID: 12407733

The persistent presence of this species across multiple years, combined with widespread independent observations sourced from multiple observers, demonstrates that *caffra* is now fully naturalized and deeply entrenched in coastal southern California. Its continued expansion northward into the Bay Area and eastward into the Central Valley strongly suggests ongoing human-mediated dispersal, most plausibly through the nursery and ornamental plant trade—an introduction pathway consistent with its emergence in Long Beach near a major international cargo port. The accumulating records from 2018–2025 reveal multigenerational persistence and broad synanthropic adaptability. Continued monitoring is warranted, as this species shows no signs of slowing its spread within the state.

Pseudovates Saussure, 1869

Species Checklist of the United States & Canada:

- *Pseudovates arizonae* Hebard, 1935
- *Pseudovates chlorophaea* (Blanchard, 1836)

Key to *Pseudovates* of the United States & Canada:

- 1 Meso/metathoracic legs lobed *P. arizonae*
- 1' Meso/metathoracic legs simple *P. chlorophaea*

Remarks. *Pseudovates arizonae* is a native and well-established element of the mantis fauna of Arizona, where it occupies xeric habitats characteristic of the Sonoran ecoregion. Its known U.S. distribution has historically been confined to Arizona, with all definitive records prior to 2019 occurring exclusively within that state. The observation from Grant County, New Mexico represents the first documented occurrence of *arizonae* outside Arizona within the United States. The mature female nymph was found in a region that is ecologically and climatically consistent with the species’ established range, characterized by open desert scrub and intermittent riparian corridors. Although this single record does not confirm the presence of a resident New Mexican population, the ecological continuity between Grant County and southeastern Arizona suggests that natural dispersal into southwestern New Mexico is plausible. Continued monitoring in the borderland region may reveal additional occurrences and clarify whether this species has expanded its native distribution eastward into New Mexico.

United States

New Mexico

- Redrock, Grant Co, NM – nymph (05.25.19) Observation ID: 25936897

Stagmomantis Saussure, 1869

Species Checklist of the United States & Canada:

- *Stagmomantis (Auromantis) limbata* (Hahn, 1835)
- *Stagmomantis (Auromantis) montana* Saussure & Zehntner, 1894
- *Stagmomantis (Longicorpus) floridensis* Davis, 1919

- Stagmomantis (Nigralora) clauseni* Garikipati, 2024
- Stagmomantis (Nigralora) wheelerii* (Thomas, 1875)
- Stagmomantis (Stagmomantis) carolina* (Linné, 1763)
- Stagmomantis (Stagmomantis) conspurcata* (Audinet-Serville, 1839)
- Stagmomantis (Stagmomantis) resacae* Anderson, 2021
- Stagmomantis (Tenuecedes) gracilipes* Rehn, 1907

Key to *Stagmomantis* Males of the United States & Canada:

- 1 Costal area of forewings entirely hyaline 2
- 1' Costal area of forewings semi-opaque to wholly opaque 5
- 2 Prozona stout, measuring 1.6–1.8 times longer than wide. Subgenital plate short, measuring <2 times length of sternite VIII. Wings lightly to heavily maculated 3
- 2' Prozona elongated, measuring 2.4 times longer than wide. Subgenital plate very elongate, measuring 2.5 times length of sternite VIII. Wings immaculate to lightly maculated. *S. floridensis*
- 3 Body length \leq 51 mm, forewing length \leq 35 mm. 4
- 3' Body length \geq 52 mm, forewing length \geq 36 mm. *S. conspurcata*
- 4 Habitus larger: body length 35.5–44 mm; forewing length 24–32.5 mm. Supracoxal dilation width to head width 2.17. Hindwing maculation scant *S. resacae*
- 4' Habitus smaller: body length 46–52 mm; forewing length 33.5–36 mm. Supracoxal dilation width to head width 1.56. Hindwing maculation dense *S. carolina*
- 5' Supracoxal dilation salient 6
- 5 Supracoxal dilation slight *S. gracilipes*
- 6 Abdominal tergites III–IV broadly edged with blackish-brown, darkening posterior third of each segment 8
- 6' Abdominal tergites monochromatic 7
- 7 Costal area of forewings distinctly widened at base, margin strongly curved *S. montana*
- 7' Costal area of forewings weakly widened at base, margin slightly curved *S. limbata*
- 8 Pronotum skewing slimmer relative to body length: pronotal width at supracoxal sulcus to pronotal length \leq 0.26. Forefemora relatively shorter given pronotal length: forefemora length to pronotal length \leq 0.50. Foretibiae armed with 8–10 posteroventral spines. Costal area of forewing green and white with variable brownish-black mottling. Occurs in eastern Sonoran Desert, AZ/NM Mountains, northern Madrean Archipelago, and Chihuahuan Desert ecoregions
..... *S. clauseni*
- 8' Pronotum slightly broader relative to body length: pronotal width at supracoxal sulcus to pronotal length \geq 0.27. Forefemora relatively longer given pronotal length: forefemora length to pronotal length \geq 0.52. Foretibiae armed with 7–8 posteroventral spines. Costal area of forewing whitish with variable blackish mottling. Occurs in southern Mediterranean California, Mojave Basin and Range, AZ/NM Plateau, and Colorado Plateau ecoregions *S. wheelerii*

Key to *Stagmomantis* Females of the United States & Canada:

- 1 Female wings reaching abdominal tergite IV or beyond 2
- 1' Female wings only reaching abdominal tergite III *S. floridensis*
- 2 Costal area of forewings narrow, measuring 0.14–0.32 times width of discoidal area 4

2'	Costal area of forewings broad, measuring 0.33–0.50 times width of discoidal area	3
3	Costal area of forewings measuring ≥ 0.45 times width of discoidal area. Lower frons 2.0 times broader than high	<i>S. montana</i>
3'	Costal area of forewings measuring ≤ 0.38 times width of discoidal area. Lower frons 3.0 times broader than high	<i>S. limbata</i>
4	Costal area measuring ≤ 0.25 times width of discoidal area	5
4'	Costal area measuring ≥ 0.30 times width of discoidal area	7
5	Body length ≤ 52 mm. Forewing length to body length 0.65–0.75	6
5'	Body length ≥ 57 mm. Forewing length to body length 0.38–0.47	<i>S. conspurcata</i>
6	Hindwings narrowly contracted. Abdomen subfusiform, measuring 5–6.5 mm at widest point	<i>S. resacae</i>
6'	Hindwings broadly expanded. Abdomen strongly fusiform, measuring 9.5–11 mm at widest point	<i>S. carolina</i>
7	Abdominal tergites III–IV broadly edged with blackish-brown. Supracoxal dilation salient	8
7'	Abdominal tergites monochromatic. Supracoxal dilation slight	<i>S. gracilipes</i>
8	Habitus proportionally larger: forewing length to pronotal length ≥ 1.00 ; forefemora width to forefemora length ≥ 0.22 ; metatibia length to metafemora length ≥ 1.20 . Foretibiae armed with 8–10 posteroventral spines. Precinctive to Sonoran and Chihuahuan deserts	<i>S. clauseni</i>
8'	Habitus proportionally smaller: forewing length to pronotal length ≤ 0.95 ; forefemora width to forefemora length ≤ 0.20 ; metatibia length to metafemora length ≤ 1.16 . Foretibiae armed with 7–8 posteroventral spines. Precinctive to the Great Basin, Colorado Plateau, Mojave Desert, San Diego Basin, and northern Baja California	<i>S. wheelerii</i>

Remarks. In Anderson’s 2019 second edition, five species of *Stagmomantis* were recognized within the nearctic fauna. Anderson (2020) subsequently redefined the subgeneric framework of the genus, establishing clear boundaries among the constituent lineages and revising diagnostic criteria used to delimit the species groups therein. In a separate work by Anderson (2020a), *conspurcata* was reinstated as a valid species following its long-standing synonymy under *carolina*. Anderson (2021b) further expanded the genus with the description of *resacae* from southern Texas, representing a distinct morphological and ecological form associated with riparian habitats. Most recently, Garikipati (2024) described *clauseni* as an additional nearctic species, supported by morphometric and genitalic differentiation. As a result of these revisions, eight species of *Stagmomantis* are now recognized as occurring within the United States and Canada. Despite these advances, *Stagmomantis* remains in poor overall taxonomic condition, with numerous unresolved lineages, historical synonymies, and inadequately defined species boundaries. A comprehensive revision of the genus is currently underway by the present author to further develop and refine the subgeneric framework established in 2020. This full treatment will be presented in the author’s forthcoming taxonomic revision of the tribe Stagmomantini.

Stagmomantis limbata remains one of the most widespread and ecologically adaptable native mantises in western North America. As presented in Anderson’s 2019 second edition, its core distribution extends across the arid and semiarid regions of the Southwest, including California, Arizona, New Mexico, Utah, and Texas. The species is well established across this western expanse, occupying habitats ranging from xeric scrub and desert riparian corridors to urbanized environments where it readily thrives. Since the 2019 publication, *limbata* has continued to expand northward and eastward into regions where it was previously unrecorded. The new state records presented here represent only the earliest documented

occurrences within each state, and should not be interpreted as isolated events. Most of these states now possess multiple counties with additional confirmed sightings, including both adults and nymphs, demonstrating ongoing dispersal and localized establishment well beyond the initial detection points. This pattern mirrors the species' known ecological flexibility and its propensity to spread along urban corridors, transportation networks, and suitable desert–grassland ecotones.

United States

Colorado

- Denver, Denver County, CO – adult male (09.03.19) Observation ID: 32088853

Florida

- Miami, Miami-Dade County, FL – adult female (09.29.25) Observation ID: 323860159

Kansas

- Merriam, Johnson County, KS – nymph (07.29.24) Observation ID: 308997090

Nevada

- Fallon, Churchill County, NV – adult female (09.13.22) Observation ID: 140125156

Oklahoma

- Black Mesa State Park, Cimarron County, OK – adult male (09.17.23) Observation ID: 183944044

Anderson reported within the 2019 second edition of *Praying Mantises of the United States and Canada* what was then believed to be an adventive *limbata* population in central Florida. The population was first detected by way of a 2015 photographic observation from Lake County that was posted to flickr.com. Subsequent research has demonstrated that this Florida population is not *limbata*, but rather *montana*— a species native to the Sierra Madre del Sur region of Guerrero and adjacent states in southern Mexico. The current distribution of *montana* in Florida spans a broad swath of central and northern counties, and while the present list enumerates only the first documented appearances, the true number of observational records now exceeds three dozen. This reflects a long-established, reproductively stable, and actively expanding population of *montana* within the Florida peninsula. An even more consequential discovery stems from the late Reinhard Ehrmann's personal photographic archive. Prior to his passing in 2025, Ehrmann contacted the present author and requested that his bibliography work on Mantodea be continued—an honor that underscores his confidence in, and support of, ongoing Nearctic mantodean research. As part of this effort, Ehrmann transferred to me his extensive digital collection of global Mantodea literature and field documentation. Among these files were thousands of photographs taken by himself and by Prof. Dr. Hermann Hans Joachim Oehlke, whose career in DDR and post-reunification Germany encompassed major contributions to Hymenoptera systematics and extensive natural history fieldwork. Within this archive is a photographic series of an adult male *montana* taken in Gainesville, Alachua County, Florida, dated 01.1989. According to Ehrmann's metadata, the photographs were taken by Oehlke during fieldwork in the region. This record predates the establishment of iNaturalist.org by almost two decades and represents the earliest known documentation of the species in the United States. It demonstrates unequivocally that *montana* has persisted in north-central Florida for over thirty-five years. Therefore, Gainesville, Alachua County, FL constitutes the initial occurrence point for this species in the U.S. Taken together, these findings evidence that *montana* is not a recent arrival but a long-term, cryptically established component of the Florida fauna. Its presence likely went unrecognized due to the absence of widely accessible citizen-science platforms prior to 2008, its superficial similarity to *limbata*, and the lack of historical Mantodea specialists working in the region. The recovery of Oehlke's and Ehrmann's field records thus not only corrects a long-standing misidentification but also highlights the essential role of photographic documentation in reconstructing the true biogeographic history of adventive mantises in North America.

United States

Florida

- Newberry, Alachua Co, FL – adult female (10.02.20) Observation ID: 61533834
- Macclenny, Baker Co, FL – adult female (10.01.20) Observation ID: 63085023

- Clermont, Lake Co, FL – adult female (09.24.15) Flickr Observation ID: 21693092415
- Williston, Levy Co, FL – adult male (09.07.23) Observation ID: 182184795
- Sparr, Marion Co, FL – adult female (10.05.19) Observation ID: 34764449
- Orlando, Orange Co, FL – adult female (09.28.16) Observation ID: 9601168
- Green Swamp Wilderness Preserve, Pasco Co, FL – adult female (10.01.15) Observation ID: 79318904
- Davenport, Polk Co, FL – adult female (11.04.22) Observation ID: 141118206
- Live Oak, Suwannee Co, FL – adult male (10.06.23) Observation ID: 186423172

02, *Stagmomantis montana* adult male. Gainesville, Alachua Co, FL 01.01.89 (Photo: Joachim Oehlke)

03, *Stagmomantis montana* adult male. Live Oak, Suwannee Co, FL 10.06.23 (Photo: birdieboo)

04, *Stagmomantis montana* adult female. Orlando, Orange Co, FL 09.28.16 (Photo: Valentyna Inshyna)

05, *Stagmomantis montana* copulating pair. Winter Garden, Orange Co, FL 09.21.22 (Photo: taarnersuaq)

06, *Stagmomantis montana* nymph. Ocala, Marion Co, FL 08.19.24 (Photo: Paul E. Thompson)

Stagmomantis floridensis remains a species of strictly peninsular affinity, with all verified historical and contemporary records confined to the state of Florida. Its distribution is closely tied to the warm temperate–subtropical mosaic of pine flatwoods, scrub, mixed hardwood hammocks, and anthropogenic edge habitats that dominate the peninsula. Until recently, no confirmed occurrences had been documented outside of Florida despite decades of intensive sampling and photographic documentation. A single out-of-state record of an adult female observed in Franklin, Louisiana represents the first known extralimital observation of *floridensis*. At present, this event is best interpreted as an isolated, adventive occurrence rather than evidence of an expanding range. There are no prior Louisiana records and no subsequent observations from St. Mary Parish or adjacent parishes that would suggest an incipient population. Nevertheless, the ecological context warrants attention. The coastal lowlands of southern Louisiana share significant climatic and vegetational continuity with peninsular Florida: mild winters, long warm seasons, high humidity, and extensive flatwoods-analog communities dominated by pines and associated understory flora. As such, the region is fully capable of supporting an established population of *floridensis* should viable oothecae or multiple individuals be introduced.

United States

Louisiana

- Franklin, St. Mary Parish, LA – adult female (09.06.25) Observation ID: 311982533

Historically, no verified populations of *Stagmomantis carolina* were known from Canada, and the species was regarded as absent from the country. The earliest Canadian record was a 2017 photograph of an adult female from Toronto, Ontario, which was initially dismissed as dubious. Subsequent observations, however, have progressively challenged that assumption. A 2019 nymph from McGregor, Ontario; a 2022 nymph from King City, Ontario; and a 2019 nymph from Montérégie, Quebec provide three independent confirmations from two provinces and across multiple, widely separated localities. Taken together, these reports validate the 2017 Toronto occurrence and indicate that *carolina* does reach Canada with some regularity. None of these observations, however, constitutes evidence of establishment: no oothecae have

been documented, no intergenerational sequence of life stages has been recorded, and no locality has produced more than one temporally spaced observation. These individuals are therefore best interpreted as adventive, non-establishing occurrences, likely derived from incidental transport of oothecae. Nonetheless, the possibility of localized Canadian populations cannot be dismissed outright. Southern Ontario and extreme southern Quebec exhibit thermal regimes broadly similar to adjacent U.S. states—particularly New York and Michigan—where *carolina* is confirmed. At present, *carolina* should be regarded as an irregular visitor to Canada, not a resident species. Continued monitoring will be necessary to determine whether the species ultimately establishes a stable northern foothold.

Canada

- Toronto, Ontario, Canada – adult female (10.01.17) Observation ID: 8245622
- McGregor, Ontario, Canada – nymph (09.05.19) Observation ID: 59190305
- King City, Ontario, Canada – nymph (08.04.22) Observation ID: 129428024
- Montréal, Québec, Canada – nymph (08.18.19) Observation ID: 201077761

In addition to the isolated and likely non-establishing Canadian occurrences, *carolina* has demonstrated a capacity for forming small, persistent adventive populations well outside its native range, particularly in the Intermountain West. Beginning in August 2018, users of the iNaturalist.org platform documented a previously unrecognized population in Salt Lake City, Utah. Verified photographs of both nymphs and adults have been recorded from the same residential district in Salt Lake City during successive summers, providing unequivocal evidence of overwintering and successful recruitment. This population is therefore multigenerational and established, and it remains confined to the urban microhabitats in which it originated. The most plausible explanation for the presence of *carolina* in the Salt Lake Valley is the introduction of oothecae via human activity. Given the ongoing commercial sale of mantis oothecae for misguided biological control, intentional release cannot be excluded. Accidental transport by way of ornamental plants or landscaping materials is equally possible. Regardless of vector, the persistence of the population demonstrates that *carolina* is capable of surviving Utah’s climate when provided favorable microhabitats such as irrigated gardens, ornamental shrubs, and anthropogenic heat islands. A second adventive population has been present in Moab, Utah, since at least October 2006. This southeastern Utah occurrence predates all other known western outliers. However, unlike the Salt Lake City population, the Moab population appears to be numerically limited: only two additional confirmed records have emerged in the nearly two decades since the original sighting. At present, the Moab population is best considered persisting but sparse, with no evidence of broader geographic expansion. In their *Field Guide to California Insects*, Will et al. (2020: 84) listed *carolina* as an introduced species “sparsely distributed in southern California and the Central Valley.” However, no confirmed collection records or verified iNaturalist observations currently substantiate its presence in California. Curiously, the same publication omits mention of *limbata*—the most widespread native mantis in the state, abundantly documented across multiple publications and collection records. Aside from the western occurrences of this species, the many northern-tier observations collectively indicate that *carolina* is undergoing a gradual but measurable northward expansion into the upper Midwestern corridor, where multiple, repeated records from Minnesota, Wisconsin, and Michigan demonstrate more than mere sporadic vagrancy. In contrast, the more northeasterly New England occurrences remain scattered and isolated, suggesting only limited footholds rather than a continuous or firmly advancing front. The new state records presented here represent only the earliest documented occurrences within each state; many of these states now possess multiple counties with subsequent sightings, reflecting ongoing dispersal and localized establishment.

United States

Maine

- Falmouth, Cumberland Co, ME – nymph (10.30.25) Observation ID: 324586738

Massachusetts

- Cambridge, Middlesex Co, MA – nymph (08.17.18) Observation ID: 143662863

Michigan

- Ann Arbor, Washtenaw Co, MI – adult female (09.12.16) Observation ID: 13198605

Minnesota

- Northfield, Rice Co, MN – nymph (09.20.19) Observation ID: 33077830
- New Hampshire
- Hampton, Rockingham Co, NH – adult male (09.29.25) Observation ID: 318653591
- Rhode Island
- Warwick, Kent Co, RI – adult male (09.27.20) Observation ID: 61039794
- South Dakota
- Vermillion, Clay Co, SD – adult female (10.04.24) Observation ID: 253663932
- Utah
- Moab, Grand Co, UT – adult female (10.20.06) Observation ID: 70368331
 - Salt Lake City, Salt Lake Co, UT – nymph (07.09.18) Observation ID: 235663161
- Vermont
- Rutland, Rutland Co, VT – nymph (09.07.24) Observation ID: 240384446
- Wisconsin
- Brookfield, Waukesha Co, WI – adult female (10.01.21) Observation ID: 135875549

Together with the *Mantis religiosa* instance of observed gutting of toxic prey items, an adult male *carolina*, a native Nearctic species not previously implicated in this specialized feeding mode, has been observed performing the same gut-extraction behavior on a late-instar *plexippus* larva. This evidence shows that gutting is not confined to a single species, trophic lineage, or biogeographic origin within Mantodea and suggests that the behavior represents a broader, phylogenetically dispersed response to chemically defended prey, thus collectively expanding the ecological relevance of the gutting framework described by Rafter et al. (2013).

07, *Stagmomantis carolina* gutting behavior. Bondurant, Polk County, IA 09.02.25 (Photo: Karen Trotter)

Stagmomantis gracilipes was long regarded as restricted to Arizona within the United States, a view reflected in Anderson's 2019 text. Since that publication, verified observations from New Mexico and Texas have expanded the documented U.S. distribution eastward into neighboring states. These records do not indicate an active range expansion; rather, they highlight the historical underdocumentation of this species, which is characterized by naturally low population densities, localized occurrence, and a superficial similarity to *limbata*. Current evidence suggests that *gracilipes* occupies suitable habitats throughout the arid basins of the southwestern U.S., with recent observations simply bringing long-overlooked portions of its true range into clearer focus. The earliest known new state records of this species are here included.

United States

New Mexico

- City of Rocks State Park, Grant Co, NM – adult male (06.12.18) Observation ID: 14117042

Texas

- Brewster Co, TX – ootheca (04.17.21) Observation ID: 74291196

Statilia Stål, 1877

Species Checklist of the United States & Canada:

- *Statilia maculata* (Thunberg, 1784)

Remarks. Since the publication of Anderson's 2019 second edition in which *maculata* was first documented as occurring in the United States, this species has exhibited a dramatic and accelerating expansion throughout the Mid-Atlantic and northeastern seaboard. The 2019 text recognized two primary points of introduction: (1) eastern Virginia around 2015–2016, where the species was first detected in the U.S. fauna, and (2) New York City, likely facilitated by substantial nursery-plant shipments originating from Maryland. The expanded dataset presented here, encompassing verified records through 2025, confirms both the persistence of these original populations and a substantial post-2019 range expansion. These records document the earliest known observations in each county but do not reflect the total volume of sightings, which now number in the hundreds across the region.

United States

Delaware

- Elkton, New Castle Co, DE – adult female (09.01.24) Observation ID: 242410607

District of Columbia

- Washington, D.C. – adult female (09.11.21) Observation ID: 94473499

Indiana

- South Bend, St. Joseph Co, IN – adult female (09.30.23) Observation ID: 185654438

Maryland

- Arnold, Anne Arundel Co, MD – nymph (08.13.21) Observation ID: 91042265
- Essex, Baltimore Co, MD – adult female (08.29.20) Observation ID: 58116243
- Sykesville, Carroll Co, MD – adult female (09.08.25) Observation ID: 312480641
- Brandywine, Charles Co, MD – adult male (09.21.24) Observation ID: 243080978
- Cambridge, Dorchester Co, MD – adult male (09.30.25) Observation ID: 317955705
- Edgewood, Harford Co, MD – adult male (10.11.24) Observation ID: 246800544
- Fulton, Howard Co, MD – nymph (05.26.22) Observation ID: 118846408
- Kent Co, MD – adult female (08.25.24) Observation ID: 237990667
- Bethesda, Montgomery Co, MD – nymph (07.09.24) Observation ID: 228317784
- Leonardtown, St. Mary's Co, MD – adult female (08.24.25) Observation ID: 308732195
- Hagerstown, Washington Co, MD – adult male (09.10.22) Observation ID: 134475357

New Jersey

- Montclair, Essex Co, NJ – adult male (09.30.24) Observation ID: 244993471
- Swedesboro, Gloucester Co, NJ – adult male (08.19.24) Observation ID: 236828394

New York

- The Bronx, Bronx Co, NY – adult female (08.29.22) Observation ID: 132875114
- Brooklyn, Kings Co, NY – adult female (11.01.18) Observation ID: 18016230
- Long Island, Queens Co, NY – adult female (10.11.21) Observation ID: 97896076
- Locust Valley, Nassau Co, NY – adult female (10.01.20) Observation ID: 61387388

North Carolina

- Raleigh, Wake Co, NC 10.04.20 – adult female (10.04.20) Observation ID: 61701576

Pennsylvania

- Penn Hills, Allegheny Co, PA – adult female (08.01.25) Observation ID: 308350469
- Codorus State Park, York Co, PA – adult male (09.24.23) Observation ID: 184765185

Virginia

- Charlottesville, Albemarle Co, VA – nymph (06.30.25) Observation ID: 294729906
- Alexandria, Alexandria Co, VA – adult female (10.03.24) Observation ID: 245380711
- Arlington, Arlington Co, VA – adult male (09.11.25) Observation ID: 313146410
- Waynesboro, Augusta Co, VA – adult female (09.28.24) Observation ID: 244534153
- Charles City Co, VA – adult female (09.11.25) Observation ID: 313207958
- Charlottesville, Charlottesville Co, VA – adult male (08.22.25) Observation ID: 308399924
- Tappahannock, Essex Co, VA – adult male (10.01.24) Observation ID: 245676544
- Lincolnia, Fairfax Co, VA – adult male (09.28.23) Observation ID: 185324448
- New Baltimore, Fauquier Co, VA – adult female (09.11.24) Observation ID: 241118152
- Manakin-Sabot, Goochland Co, VA – adult female (10.31.23) Observation ID: 190445365
- Ashland, Hanover Co, VA – adult female (10.25.18) Observation ID: 17989404
- Hopewell, Hopewell Co, VA – adult male (09.22.25) Observation ID: 315942713
- King George Co, VA – adult male (10.23.25) Observation ID: 322567768
- King William Co, VA – nymph (07.06.25) Observation ID: 299958695
- Sterling, Loudoun Co, VA – nymph (07.21.21) Observation ID: 88037595
- Lovingston, Nelson Co, VA – adult male (11.05.22) Observation ID: 141174944
- New Kent Co, VA – adult female (10.24.22) Observation ID: 142385669
- Orange, Orange Co, VA – adult female (10.21.21) Observation ID: 100499150
- Powhatan Co, VA – adult female (11.27.25) Observation ID: 328503582
- Manassas, Prince William Co, VA – adult female (08.23.21) Observation ID: 92278052
- Staunton, Staunton Co, VA – adult female (10.15.20) Observation ID: 62695569
- Winchester, Winchester Co, VA – adult male (09.26.24) Observation ID: 244175786

The Virginia–Maryland population has spread westward into the Piedmont (e.g., Hanover, Fauquier, Goochland counties), northward into Pennsylvania (York County), and northeastward into New Jersey. Maryland now exhibits widespread establishment across numerous counties, including Anne Arundel, Harford, Carroll, Charles, Howard, Baltimore, Montgomery, St. Mary’s, Washington, and Dorchester, demonstrating multigenerational persistence and annual reappearance. Delaware (New Castle County) and the District of Columbia likewise record established populations. The New York population continues to produce repeated annual sightings across Manhattan, Brooklyn, the Bronx, and Queens, closely matching the colonization pattern noted between 2017 and 2019 but now with substantially greater spatial coverage. Additional counties in New Jersey (Essex, Gloucester) and Pennsylvania (Allegheny, York) demonstrate westward diffusion beyond the original New York focus. Two notable developments since 2019 include the appearance of *maculata* well outside the previously inferred invasion corridor, including occurrences in Indiana (St. Joseph County) and North Carolina (Wake County), which further indicate that isolated dispersal events are occurring beyond the primary invasion corridor. These records suggest either long-distance human-mediated transport, likely via the horticultural trade, or the existence of multiple independent introduction events. The species’ frequent association with landscaped environments, nurseries, ornamental plantings, and urban parks remains consistent with its suspected mode of dispersal. The chronological sequence of verified first county records from 2019–2025 indicates annual recurrence, successful overwintering, multigenerational establishment, and continuous

colonization of new areas. Collectively, these records demonstrate that *maculata* is now firmly established in the eastern United States and is rapidly expanding its Nearctic distribution. Continued monitoring is warranted, as both its documented spread and increasing frequency in new localities strongly suggest that this species' Nearctic range will continue to grow in the coming years.

Tenodera Burmeister, 1838

Species Checklist of the United States & Canada:

- *Tenodera angustipennis* Saussure, 1869
- *Tenodera sinensis* Saussure, 1871

Key to *Tenodera* of the United States & Canada:

- 1 Prozonal margins subparallel, anterior margin broadly and bluntly rounded, middle of prozona spanning slightly wider than or equal to width of metazona, supracoxal dilation slight. Hindwings narrow, anal area hyaline to lightly infumate. Prosternum with orange-colored maculation between forecoxae *T. angustipennis*
- 1' Prozonal margins converging, anterior margin narrowly tapered, middle of prozona spanning significantly wider than width of metazona, supracoxal dilation marked. Hindwings broad, anal area heavily maculated against suffused background. Prosternum with yellow-colored maculation between forecoxae *T. sinensis*

Remarks. *Tenodera sinensis* is the most frequently transported and commercially disseminated mantis species in the Western Hemisphere. For at least the last forty years, and likely longer, its oothecae have been mass-marketed for supposed biological pest control, first to commercial orchards, vineyards, and large agricultural operations, and later to the general public through garden centers, nurseries, and online retailers. By the early 1980s, oothecae of *sinensis* were already being sold in local nurseries throughout the United States, and the species had become firmly embedded in the culture of misguided biological control promotion. As documented in both editions of Anderson's 2018 and 2019 texts, the continental spread of *sinensis* is almost entirely anthropogenic and seldom corresponds to natural dispersal patterns. Given the massive and ongoing scale of these introductions, *sinensis* can appear virtually anywhere in the United States or Canada, irrespective of habitat suitability or climatic constraints. Some populations persist for multiple generations; others collapse after a single season; and many areas experience yearly re-introductions from commercially purchased oothecae. These perpetual cycles of artificial augmentation render any attempt to chart a meaningful state- or county-level distribution ecologically uninformative. For this reason, no locality list is provided here, as such a record would inevitably reflect human commerce more than natural biogeography. Despite this, two extralimital observations from Mexico are noteworthy, as this species has never before been charted to occur in that country. Both represent adventive individuals whose presence is almost certainly attributable to the same commercial pathways responsible for the species' proliferation in the United States. These isolated Mexican occurrences do not indicate establishment but instead highlight the international reach of commercial horticultural and agricultural supply chains in distributing *sinensis* far beyond its native East Asian range.

Mexico

- Mexico City, Ciudad de México, Mexico – adult male (09.23.21) Observation ID: 119535678
- Lagos de Moreno, Jalisco, Mexico – adult female (10.19.16) Observation ID: 4395828

Tenodera angustipennis has experienced a distributional trajectory parallel to but far less extensive than that of *sinensis*. For several decades, *angustipennis* has been intermittently transported through the same commercial horticultural and agricultural channels responsible for the widespread dissemination of *sinensis*, including the sale of oothecae in nurseries and through online auction networks such as Ebay.com. Although the volume of commercial movement is markedly lower, these mechanisms have nevertheless facilitated sporadic introductions far outside the species' native Asian range. The first

confirmed records of *angustipennis* in Canada are presented here. These findings represent the northernmost occurrences known to date and demonstrate that the commercial vectors affecting *sinensis* are now contributing, albeit at a smaller scale, to the adventive spread of *angustipennis* as well.

Canada

- Welland, Ontario, Canada – adult male (09.30.25) Observation ID: 317859794
- Noyan, Quebec, Canada – ootheca (06.19.22) Observation ID: 122970974

Thespis Audinet-Serville, 1831

Species Checklist of the United States & Canada:

- *Thespis parva* (Gmelin, 1788)

Remarks. *Oligonicella scudderi* (Saussure, 1870) was reviewed in detail by Anderson (2022b), who conducted a comprehensive historical assessment of the nomenclature associated with *Oligonicella* Giglio-Tos, 1915. That analysis concluded that *scudderi* is conspecific with *parva*, thereby rendering *Oligonicella* a junior synonym of *Thespis* and necessitating the formal transfer of all included species accordingly. Anderson further argued that the extreme intrapopulational and intersexual variation previously ascribed to *scudderi* reflects not mere polymorphism, but a broader unresolved species complex within *parva*. The variation observed among males, particularly in body size and wing development, cannot be adequately explained by intraspecific variability alone. Insufficient comparative material, especially of females and oothecae, prevents resolution of the complex at present. Future examination of sympatric populations across the southeastern United States and Great Plains, incorporating additional life history data, is required to determine the extent of divergence within *parva*. Pending such analyses, *parva* is regarded as a complex encompassing the forms previously treated under *scudderi*. This species continues to exhibit a relatively stable and localized distribution within the United States, consistent with the range outlined in Anderson’s 2019 text. Since that publication, only two outlying records have appeared. These isolated observations do not indicate any meaningful range expansion and instead fall well within the broader ecological envelope long associated with the species.

United States

North Carolina

- Taylorsville, Alexander Co, NC – adult male (10.05.18) Observation ID: 19355238

Tennessee

- J. Percy Priest Lake, Rutherford Co, TN – adult female (08.12.22) Observation ID: 130587133

Thesprotia Stal, 1877

Species Checklist of the United States & Canada:

- *Thesprotia graminis* (Scudder, 1877)

Remarks. McGregor et al. (2019) documented the life cycle of *graminis*, wherein an ootheca that was oviposited by a captive female was described as being “laid parthenogenetically”. Anderson subsequently corresponded with the lead author of this study, who noted that the captive female in question was raised from a later instar nymph that was captured locally. Upon maturity, the female reportedly oviposited an ootheca without having any contact with a male as an adult. However, McGregor (2020) noted that this ootheca was never observed to have yielded nymphs. As such, the reference to parthenogenesis within this study is not evidenced and the ootheca in question is considered to be an infertile oviposition from an unmated female, an occurrence that is widespread among Mantodea. As such, there is no verified evidence of parthenogenetic reproduction in *graminis*. The distribution of *graminis* has remained essentially unchanged since the range summary provided in Anderson’s 2019 text, which documented this species as confined to the Gulf Coast states. Since that publication, only a single outlying occurrence has been recorded.

United States

North Carolina

- Lowell, Gaston Co, NC – adult male (05.17.20) Observation ID: 46321180

Yersiniops Hebard, 1931

Species Checklist of the United States & Canada:

- *Yersiniops solitarius* (Scudder, 1896)
- *Yersiniops sophronicus* (Rehn & Hebard, 1908)

Key to *Yersiniops* of the United States & Canada:

- 1 Pronotum elongated, metazona measuring twice as long as prozona. Dorsal surface of compound eyes greatly extended into acute points, sharply inclining juxtaocular region and most of vertex. Straightened middle portion of vertex much narrower than lower frons. Distribution range restricted to central and southern Arizona *Y. sophronicus*
- 1' Pronotum stout, metazona measuring at most 1.5 times as long as prozona. Dorsal surface of compound eyes moderately extended into acute points, moderately inclining juxtaocular region and some of vertex. Straightened middle portion of vertex as wide as or wider than lower frons. Distribution range extended throughout New Mexico and into western Texas, central Colorado, and eastern Arizona *Y. solitarius*

ADVENTIVE SPECIES

The Nearctic region hosts a relatively small number of native mantis species when compared to the extraordinary diversity of the Neotropical region to the south. Yet, despite this natural limitation, the Nearctic fauna has been increasingly influenced by human intervention. Many of the most common mantis species now encountered across North America are not native at all, but rather were deliberately introduced during the late 19th to mid-20th century under the persistent misconception that Mantodea could serve as effective biological control agents against pest insects. This notion, which remains widely accepted by gardeners, farmers, and even some entomologists, has proven biologically unsound. As any brief review of Mantodea observations on citizen-science platforms such as iNaturalist readily demonstrates, praying mantises are generalist predators with no preference for agricultural pests over other arthropods. They attack virtually any moving organism that falls within an appropriate size ratio, including beneficial pollinators, other predatory insects, and even small vertebrates such as hummingbirds, lizards, and salamanders. Their opportunistic hunting behavior, often conducted from perches on flower heads where insect activity is concentrated, places them in direct conflict with native pollinator communities. Nevertheless, oothecae of the largest and most ecologically disruptive species continue to be sold commercially each year for supposed “natural pest control,” perpetuating their spread and ecological impact.

Among the well-established introduced species in the Nearctic region are *Tenodera sinensis*, *Tenodera angustipennis*, *Iris oratoria*, and *Mantis religiosa*—each now firmly integrated into local faunas across broad geographic ranges. Anderson’s 2018 first edition further documented the emergence of newly established, intergenerational populations of additional non-native taxa, including *Liturgusa maya* and *Miomantis caffra*. The 2019 second edition added records of newly established, intergenerational populations of *Statilia maculata*. In 2021, Anderson further reported the occurrence of *Acontista cordillerae* within Florida. Beyond these documented establishments, a growing number of additional non-native mantis species have been recorded throughout the Nearctic region in recent years. However, all of these occurrences are represented by isolated individuals that have not yet demonstrated evidence of establishment or reproduction, and are therefore considered adventive. The following accounts summarize

these verified sightings and serve to illustrate the increasing frequency with which exotic Mantodea are arriving in North America. These cases, while presently lacking evidence of permanence, underscore the ease with which non-native taxa continue to enter the region through accidental transport and international commerce, highlighting the need for continued monitoring and accurate taxonomic identification of these transient introductions.

Hierodula patellifera Audinet-Serville, 1838

Initial Occurrence Site: Linwood, Atlantic Co, NJ

Remarks. Five separate iNaturalist.org observations of *patellifera* have been documented from four different states, all of which are of adult female individuals.

United States

California

- Hayward, Alameda Co, CA – adult female (08.30.21) Observation ID: 93123522
- Norwalk, Los Angeles Co, CA – adult female (12.12.21) Observation ID: 103010407

Florida

- Orlando, Orange Co, FL – adult female (04.21.22) Observation ID: 112301066

New Jersey

- Linwood, Atlantic Co, NJ – adult female (10.24.19) Observation ID: 34836217

Pennsylvania

- Erie, Erie Co, PA – adult female (08.18.23) Observation ID: 240078133

The first known Nearctic record of *patellifera* was an adult female photographed in Linwood, New Jersey—an observation that marks the initial occurrence of this species within the United States. Since that time, four additional adult females have been documented on iNaturalist.org from widely separated localities: California (two independent records), Florida and Pennsylvania. Each of these records consists solely of a single adult female, and no oothecae, nymphs, adult males, or additional individuals have been observed in any of these states. At present, *patellifera* therefore remains strictly adventive, with no evidence of reproduction or establishment in the Nearctic region. Among the five occurrence sites, the pathways and volumes of invasive species interceptions differ dramatically. The Port of Los Angeles (together with adjacent Long Beach) stands as one of the highest-risk entry points in the United States for invasive species, handling roughly 40% of the nation’s containerized imports and consistently ranking first or second nationally for USDA-APHIS and CBP detections of quarantine pests, including insects, plant pathogens, and mollusks. Norwalk and Hayward, California, while lacking their own seaports, lie close to major container facilities (Norwalk to the Los Angeles/Long Beach complex and Hayward to the Port of Oakland) and host numerous import warehouses and air-cargo operations, making both secondary but still significant sites for pest interceptions in transiting commodities. In contrast, Erie, Pennsylvania; Linwood, New Jersey; and Orlando, Florida possess no major international cargo ports and record very few or virtually no maritime or air-cargo invasive species interceptions; any rare findings in these areas are almost always linked to passenger baggage, international mail, or small-volume propagative material rather than large-scale commercial cargo. Consequently, within this group, only the greater Los Angeles region (including Norwalk) and, to a lesser extent, the Hayward/Oakland area function as meaningful hotspots for the interception of invasive species arriving via international trade. Ecologically, these occurrence sites share characteristics common to adventive mantis occurrences: urban or suburban environments with abundant ornamental vegetation and warm microhabitats created by human structures. These features can allow a gravid female to survive long enough to be encountered, even if the broader climate is marginal for long-term persistence. However, in none of these localities has *patellifera* demonstrated the capacity to overwinter, oviposit viable oothecae, or produce subsequent generations. Given the absence of other stages of life or repeated annual sightings of adults, there is no evidence that *patellifera* has established a multigenerational population anywhere in the United States. These occurrences almost certainly represent interceptive events—isolated arrivals of single individuals transported inadvertently through commercial channels. Continued monitoring through platforms such as

iNaturalist will be essential to determine whether future introductions remain sporadic or if this species ultimately gains a foothold in the Nearctic region.

08, *Hierodula patellifera* adult female. Erie, Erie Co, PA 08.18.23 (Photo: Jaxsen Rinke)

09, *Hierodula patellifera* adult female. Hayward, Alameda Co, CA 08.30.21 (Photo: k_lida)

10, *Hierodula patellifera* adult female. Linwood, Atlantic Co, NJ 10.24.19 (Photo: atticgem)

11, *Hierodula patellifera* adult female. Norwalk, Los Angeles Co, CA 12.12.21 (Photo: Mahyini Mathew)

12, *Hierodula patellifera* adult female. Orlando, Orange Co, FL 04.21.22 (Photo: jjnavarro1)

Hierodula transcaucasica Brunner, 1878

Initial Occurrence Site: Tuxedo Park, Orange Co, NY

Remarks. A single iNaturalist.org observation of *transcaucasica* has been documented from New York.

United States

New York

- Tuxedo Park, Orange Co, NY – adult female (10.09.23) Observation ID: 186905769

This lone record currently constitutes the only verified occurrence of *transcaucasica* within the Nearctic region. No additional observations have been recorded from North America, and there is no indication of reproduction or establishment. Accordingly, this taxon remains strictly adventive in the United States. The appearance of *transcaucasica* in New York is notable in light of the species' rapid and well-documented spread throughout Europe during the past decade. Since the early 2010s, *transcaucasica* has expanded across numerous European countries, with new national and regional records published annually. Tuxedo Park lies within the greater New York metropolitan corridor, an area closely tied to major international shipping and logistics routes, making unintentional importation the most plausible pathway of arrival. At present, there is no evidence that *transcaucasica* has propagated or persisted beyond this single event. Continued monitoring of urban and suburban areas near major ports, combined with the ongoing contributions of citizen scientists on platforms such as iNaturalist, will be essential to determine whether this species remains a transient arrival or if future introductions ultimately lead to regional establishment.

13, *Hierodula transcaucasica* adult female. Tuxedo Park, Orange Co, NY 10.09.23 (Photo: Timothy Kouloumpas)

Rivetina sp. Berland & Chopard, 1922

Initial Occurrence Site: Marshall Canyon Regional Park, Los Angeles Co, CA

Remarks. A single iNaturalist.org observation of *Rivetina* sp. has been documented from California.

United States

California

- Marshall Canyon Regional Park, Los Angeles Co, CA – nymph (07.05.19) Observation ID: 36406474

Because the photographed specimen is an immature individual lacking the definitive adult morphological features required for species-level determination, this observation cannot be confidently assigned to any of the currently recognized species within *Rivetina*. This observation represents the only verified occurrence of the genus in the Nearctic region. The genus *Rivetina* is native to central Asia, with species distributed across Xinjiang (western China), Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, and portions of southern Russia. These regions are characterized by arid to semi-arid steppe, foothill desert, and montane xeric environments—habitats that share notable ecological similarities with portions of southern California. The occurrence site in Los Angeles County lies within a Mediterranean–arid transitional zone marked by hot, dry summers, sparse vegetation, and rugged terrain. Such conditions resemble the dry foothills and steppe habitats occupied by *Rivetina* in its native range and may explain the species’ ability to survive long enough for detection following accidental introduction. Despite these broad ecological parallels, there is no evidence that *Rivetina* has established a population in the United States. No subsequent observations have been reported from California or elsewhere in the Nearctic region since the 2019 record. The lack of repeated sightings and the absence of any life stages beyond the lone nymph strongly indicate that this event represents a single, non-persistent incursion, most likely facilitated through accidental transport associated with international travel.

14, *Rivetina* sp. nymph. Marshall Canyon Regional Park, Los Angeles Co, CA 07.05.19 (Photo: Ali Maatouk)

Sphodromantis viridis (Forsk., 1775)

Initial Occurrence Site: Tucson, Pima Co, AZ

Remarks. A single iNaturalist.org observation of *viridis* has been documented from Arizona.

United States

Arizona

- Tucson, Pima Co, AZ – adult female (10.06.20) Observation ID: 61871653

Native to the Mediterranean Basin and adjacent arid zones of North Africa and the Middle East, *viridis* occupies warm xeric environments characterized by hot, dry summers, mild winters, and patchy vegetation—conditions that bear superficial similarity to portions of the Sonoran Desert surrounding Tucson. Although southern Arizona is landlocked, its climate includes extended periods of high heat and low humidity that approximate certain ecological elements of the species’ natural habitats. However, unlike many other adventive Mantodea that arrive through international cargo routes or coastal ports, the appearance of *viridis* in inland Tucson almost certainly reflects escape or release from the captive-breeding community, where this species is both common and widely kept. This species is one of the most frequently bred Old World mantises in the global hobbyist market, and escapes from captive settings—including private breeding collections, transport between breeders, or accidental loss during maintenance—represent the most plausible mechanism for this occurrence. Despite the climatic tolerance of *viridis*, there has been no subsequent spread or additional sightings in Arizona or elsewhere in the United States. No multigenerational or overwintering population has been detected, and no corroborating life stages have been observed. As such, this record appears to represent a one-time incidental escape rather than the beginning of establishment. Continued monitoring of urban and peri-urban areas may clarify whether further introductions occur, but current evidence indicates that *viridis* remains an isolated, non-persistent adventive in the Nearctic region.

15, *Sphodromantis viridis* adult female. Tucson, Pima Co, AZ 10.06.20 (Photo: jakecr11)

Stagmomantis (Oromantis) vicina Saussure, 1870

Initial Occurrence Site: Corpus Christi, Nueces Co, TX

Remarks. A single iNaturalist.org observation of *vicina* has been documented from Texas.

United States

Texas

- Corpus Christi, Nueces Co, TX – adult male (10.14.20) Observation ID: 62567166

Callimantis floridana Scudder, 1896 was established from a single male specimen described from Florida. Blatchley (1920: 123) later provided a supplemental account based on a male taken near Brownsville, Texas, noting that the female remained unknown and the broader range of the species undetermined. Examination of Scudder's holotype now demonstrates that *floridana* is morphologically identical to the male holotype of *vicina* and should therefore be treated as conspecific with that species. Although *floridana* is currently listed as a junior synonym under *venusta* Saussure & Zehntner, 1894, this placement is incorrect and will be formally revised in the present author's forthcoming taxonomic revision of the tribe Stagmomantini. A single modern record attributable to *vicina* has been documented on iNaturalist.org from Corpus Christi. This observation is noteworthy because it lies within the region historically associated with the enigmatic *floridana* material. It is plausible that this individual represents a remnant or low-density population that may have first been encountered by Blatchley, whose specimen lacks precise locality data, or even by Scudder, whose treatment of *floridana* hints at a Gulf Coast origin. The scattered and temporally distant records—Scudder's original indication, Blatchley's Brownsville male, and the recent Corpus Christi observation—collectively suggest either: (1) the existence of a small, long-standing population of *vicina* along the Gulf of America, or (2) multiple, independent incursions of this species into the region over the past century. No additional historical specimens or contemporary observations are known, and the scarcity of records is itself suspicious. Whether the Gulf Coast occurrences reflect an overlooked, persistent population or repeated adventive introductions remains unresolved.

16, *Stagmomantis (Oromantis) vicina* adult male. Corpus Christi, Nueces Co, TX 10.14.20 (Photo: zthenrunner)

Tenodera australasiae (Leach, 1814)

Initial Occurrence Site: Port Vincent, Livingston Parish, LA

Remarks. A single iNaturalist.org observation of *australasiae* has been documented from Louisiana.

United States

Louisiana

- Port Vincent, Livingston Parish, LA – adult female (04.02.21) Observation ID: 74223837

This record constitutes the only verified occurrence of *australasiae* within the Nearctic region. No additional observations have been recorded since, and there is no indication of reproduction, establishment, or persistence. Accordingly, *australasiae* remains strictly adventive in the United States. Native to Australia and widely distributed throughout that region, *australasiae* is not known to be involved in horticultural or agricultural trade practices that might encourage intentional importation. This stands in contrast to *Tenodera sinensis* and *Tenodera angustipennis*, two Asian congeners that are now deeply established across broad swaths of the United States. Those species proliferated following decades of intentional introduction and widespread commercial sale of their oothecae under the persistent but erroneous belief that mantises act as effective biological control agents. No such misconception is associated with *australasiae*, and there is no evidence that it has been deliberately distributed or sold within the U.S.

17, *Tenodera australasiae* adult female. Port Vincent, Livingston Parish, LA 04.02.21 (Photo: madiwillson)

HETEROSPECIFIC MATE ATTRACTION

Heterospecific mate attraction among Mantodea arises from a confluence of life-history traits, sensory ecology, and extreme sexual dimorphism characteristic of the order. Although mantises are widely recognized for elaborate predatory adaptations and, in some taxa, for sexual cannibalism, their mating system is equally shaped by profound asymmetries between the sexes. These asymmetries form the primary ecological backdrop against which heterospecific encounters occur.

Mantodea exhibit some of the most pronounced sexual dimorphism among insects. Adult females tend to be substantially larger, heavier, and more robust than conspecific males. Their ecology is fundamentally shaped by sedentary reproductive strategy. Mature females do not actively seek mates; instead, they remain stationary, often for extended periods, awaiting the arrival of males. Many are physiologically optimized for ootheca production rather than locomotion. Their wings may be shortened or absent and even macropterous females often do not fly. This reduced mobility, combined with heightened hunting capacity associated with larger body size, enables females to consistently acquire the greater nutritional intake required for egg production. They capture and subdue substantially larger prey items than males, often with greater frequency and aggression, traits that scale with metabolic demands of reproduction.

Males, by contrast, are engineered by selection for scramble competition mating systems. They do not defend territories, do not monopolize resources needed by females, and do not engage in ritualized or physical combat with rival males. The dominant competitive mode is therefore not male–male aggression, but speed, efficiency, and sensory acumen in locating receptive females. Males are typically far more active at night than females and invest their limited adult lifespan and minimal energetic budget into near-continuous mate searching. They are lighter, more gracile, far more agile, and rely heavily on flight, long-range detection, and rapid movement. Their smaller size reduces energetic maintenance and allows

sustained locomotor effort. Prey capture in males is correspondingly reduced in scale; they target smaller, easier prey, ingest less overall, and function physiologically as low-investment, high-mobility reproductive units relative to females.

Male Mantodea typically possess markedly enlarged and more functional ocelli relative to females. In many species, females exhibit heavily reduced ocelli or lack them entirely, whereas males display large, prominent ocellar lenses situated to maximize dorsal–ventral light contrast detection. Ocelli are exceptionally fast photoreceptors with wide visual fields and extremely low spatial resolution. Their primary function lies not in object discrimination but in detecting horizon orientation via brightness gradients between the sky and the ground. This information feeds directly to motor centers governing wing-steering muscles and cervical musculature, enabling rapid stabilization of flight pitch and roll on millisecond timescales—far faster than compound-eye pathways can manage. Such reflexive attitude-control capacity is indispensable to males, whose scramble competition strategy requires sustained nocturnal flight, rapid maneuvers through complex vegetation, and the ability to navigate precisely toward distant pheromone cues. By contrast, sedentary females, which are often heavy, gravid, and flight-limited, experience little selective pressure to maintain functional ocelli. Their reproductive mode does not depend on flight navigation, horizon detection, or rapid course correction; their survival and fecundity benefit more from cryptic stillness and predatory capacity than from locomotor precision. Male antennae are similarly exaggerated. In numerous taxa, males exhibit longer, more ornate, or more densely sensillar antennae than females. These adaptations allow males to detect and track pheromone plumes emitted by receptive females, following concentration gradients across fluctuating nighttime air currents.

Visual detection appears to be the primary trigger for male mounting attempts across the order. Males in high-density scramble systems display an indiscriminate mounting reflex toward any similarly sized object in motion or silhouette, including sympatric females and males of other species, nymphs, and even other males of the same species. The visual system in Mantodea is simply not optimized for fine-scale species recognition under the time pressures of scramble competition. Instead, it is optimized for movement detection, contrast, and basic form—not taxonomic identity. Cues within the visual signature of a receptive adult female (possibly UV reflectance patterns, cuticular polarization signatures, or wing-position silhouette) distinguishes them from prey or predators, reducing attack responses and eliciting mounting. However, these cues are broad enough that males routinely misidentify heterospecifics, resulting in frequent erroneous mating attempts.

When males cannot visually confirm females during daylight or in habitats where females remain deeply concealed, they rely almost entirely on pheromone gradients during nocturnal flight. Receptive females release pheromones primarily when mate encounters have not occurred—either due to low population density, environmental barriers, or high levels of crypsis. Once a male has already arrived, pheromone emission becomes unnecessary; however, some species exploit pheromonal signals more opportunistically and lure males as prey rather than mating partners.

This reliance on fast, coarse visual triggers and generalist pheromone tracking creates an inherently error-prone system, particularly in assemblages of closely related or similarly sized taxa. Males, driven by short lifespans, low energy reserves, and intense temporal competition, routinely accept the cost of false positives rather than risk missing a legitimate mating opportunity. The sensory and behavioral asymmetries between the sexes therefore reinforce the conditions under which heterospecific mating attempts occur: males act quickly and broadly, while females act passively and selectively, with little incentive to avoid or correct male identification errors.

Heterospecific mating in Mantodea thus tends to emerge through three principal mechanisms. First, scramble competition inherently reduces discrimination accuracy. Males searching rapidly and under

intense time pressure encounter females opportunistically; the cost of pausing to evaluate species identity may exceed the cost of an occasional heterospecific attempt. Second, female behavior does not strongly regulate mate identity; most females remain stationary and rely on male approach, meaning that species-specific mate guarding or species-specific sexual displays are largely absent. Third, the sensory modalities used during mate location—primarily motion cues and secondarily pheromonal detection—are not always strictly species-specific, particularly in sympatric assemblages of closely related taxa with overlapping chemical signatures or similar silhouettes. As a result, males with high urgency and low longevity may attempt copulation with any female-shaped or pheromone-emitting target encountered.

These interactions may result in several outcomes. In some instances, males are cannibalized before any successful copulation attempt, as the female's feeding response is triggered irrespective of male species identity. In others, males may successfully mount and attempt copulation, but genital incompatibility prevents insemination; Mantodea exhibit complex genital architecture that often restricts interspecific fertilization. Occasionally, however, partial genital compatibility may permit mechanical coupling, though hybridization remains exceedingly rare and likely unviable across most of the order. More commonly, heterospecific mating attempts constitute an energetic and reproductive waste for males (a predictable cost within scramble systems) and a negligible cost for females, who incur little risk, lose no mobility advantage, and sometimes gain the nutritional value of an overeager male. This asymmetry likely maintains selection pressures that permit, rather than prevent, heterospecific attempts.

Heterospecific mating in Mantodea is best understood not as an aberration but as an emergent property of the order's unique reproductive ecology. Strong sexual dimorphism, sedentary and predatory females, and mobile, short-lived, energetically constrained males converge to produce a system where male urgency overrides stringent species recognition. The interplay of sensory limitations, overlapping mating cues in sympatric environments, and the fundamentally opportunistic male strategy ensures that heterospecific encounters remain a routine byproduct of Mantodea ethology. Such events illuminate broader evolutionary dynamics within the order, offering insight into mate searching, reproductive investment, species boundaries, and sexual selection pressures that continue to shape the extraordinary diversity of praying mantises across the globe.

Taken together, the behavioral ecology, sensory asymmetries, and scramble-driven urgency that characterize Mantodea reproduction create a system in which species boundaries exert only weak constraints on male mating behavior. However, all available evidence indicates that this breakdown of mate discrimination is taxonomically constrained: *every verified instance of heterospecific mating within the Neartic realm originates exclusively within the family Mantidae*. This pattern is borne out unequivocally in field observations. Within Mantidae, heterospecific mating attempts occur across all geographic contexts and taxonomic groupings: native males readily mount adventive or non-native females, while introduced males indiscriminately pursue native taxa with equal frequency. In many instances, these interactions involve striking size disparities, with diminutive males attempting to mount females many times their mass. Most of these events consist solely of mounting behavior, lacking terminal flexion, genital interaction, or any mechanized effort toward copulation. However, there are several observations that demonstrate males attempting copulation with or achieving full genital engagement with heterospecific females. *The confinement of this behavior to Mantidae provides critical evidence that the sensory and behavioral mechanisms producing heterospecific attempts are not universal across Mantodea but reflect lineage-specific traits within this family*. These cases are documented here and provide critical insight into the limits of mechanical compatibility within Mantidae. The following section presents a detailed compilation of these observations, illustrating the breadth, frequency, and character of heterospecific mating events recorded across this family.

Mantis religiosa Linné, 1758

Remarks. Heterospecific mate attraction has been documented in *religiosa*, underscoring the species' reliance on rapid, visually mediated mate-discrimination processes characteristic of Mantidae. An adult male *religiosa* has been recorded mounting an adult female *Stagmomantis limbata*, despite the two species sharing no evolutionary history in the Nearctic region, as *religiosa* is native to the Mediterranean basin of Europe, whereas *limbata* is endemic to western North America. Their interaction is possible only because *religiosa* has become well established in North America following introduction. Both belong to Mantidae, the sole mantid family in which heterospecific mating attempts are known in the U.S., yet the two lineages diverged too deeply for any historical mate-recognition compatibility to have been conserved. Additional records reveal male *religiosa* mounting adult females of *Tenodera sinensis* in regions where the two species are now sympatric. Although both taxa have long been introduced in the United States, *religiosa* from Europe and *sinensis* from the Indo-Malaysian region share no evolutionary background, further demonstrating that heterospecific interactions arise independently of shared lineage or geographic origin. Notably, a male *religiosa* has also been observed attempting copulation with a male *sinensis*, indicating that male *religiosa* initiate mounting behavior using visual triggers alone; pheromones appear to play no role during this initial phase of scramble mate competition. *Mantis religiosa* is one of the few Nearctic-occurring mantids with a well-documented courtship sequence when approaching conspecific females. This ritualized approach involves a series of measured, species-specific movements that typically elicit a corresponding acceptance or reduction in aggression from a receptive *religiosa* female. In all heterospecific encounters recorded to date, it remains unknown whether males attempted to employ this courtship routine before mounting. However, it is likely that none of the heterospecific individuals exhibited the acceptance behaviors that conspecific females reliably display in response to the male's courtship gestures. This strongly suggests that the male *religiosa* either bypassed the courtship display entirely or overrode the information provided by the female's non-acceptance, proceeding directly to mounting. Such behavior is consistent with the sensory ecology of scramble competition, in which speed and opportunity often supersede discrimination. Together, these observations show that *religiosa* males exhibit broad, nondiscriminatory mounting responses toward heterospecifics and even heterosex conspecifics, consistent with the sensory and behavioral profile that characterizes Mantidae mating dynamics.

18, *Mantis religiosa* adult male mounting *Stagmomantis limbata* adult female. La Cienega, Santa Fe Co, NM 08.31.24 (Photo: Ben Shulman)

19, *Mantis religiosa* adult male mounting and attempting copulation with *Tenodera sinensis* adult male, eliciting an unfavorable response. Allendale, Ottawa Co, MI 08.22.22 (Photo: Ian Pope)

20, *Mantis religiosa* adult male mounting *Tenodera sinensis* adult female. Toronto, Ontario, Canada 10.01.23 (Photo: Paul Prior)

Additional observations of adult male *religiosa* vs adult female *sinensis*

- Caledonia, Kent Co, MI (08.25.20) Observation ID: 57640475

Stagmomantis (Auromantis) limbata (Hahn, 1835)

Remarks. Observations of heterospecific mating behavior in *Stagmomantis limbata* provides rare insight into the functional thresholds of genital compatibility within Mantidae. One notable observation involves an adult male *limbata* successfully engaging in copulation with an adult female *wheelerii* in southern Arizona, where both species naturally co-occur. It remains unknown whether such unions can yield viable hybrid offspring. This record nonetheless demonstrates that *limbata* males can progress beyond simple mounting and achieve full genital engagement with closely related taxa. Multiple field observations extend these interactions across even further unrelated genera. In northern California, adult male *limbata* have been recorded mounting adult females of *Mantis religiosa* in regions where both species are now sympatric following introduction of *religiosa* several decades prior. Additional observations detail two *limbata* males simultaneously mounting an adult *Tenodera sinensis* female—an exceptional example of scramble-competition polygyny involving a non-native species. Such events highlight the highly opportunistic and visually driven mate-search strategies of *limbata* males, which appear to override discrimination even toward significantly larger or evolutionarily unrelated mates. More remarkably, two independent observations document successful copulation between adult male *limbata* and adult female *religiosa*. Unlike the more common mounting-only events seen between unrelated mantid genera, these cases proceeded to confirmed genital anchoring. This is of particular functional significance. While *Mantis* and *Stagmomantis* differ substantially in aspects of male genital morphology, certain components used for mechanical alignment, insertion, and anchorage appear sufficiently comparable. Successful anchoring indicates that the differences in the male anchoring structures are not prohibitive barriers in early copulatory stages. However, the more pronounced divergence in the internal genitalic processes and the configuration of associated sclerites strongly suggests that spermatophore deposition would likely fail. Thus, while mechanical coupling can occur, reproductive completion almost certainly cannot. From a morphological standpoint, these cases provide empirical evidence for the range of acceptable variability in male genitalia before anchoring becomes impossible—critical information for understanding the functional evolution of genital complexity in Mantidae.

21, *Stagmomantis limbata* adult male mounting *Mantis religiosa* adult female. Davis, Yolo Co, CA 09.11.20 (Photo: Lohit Garikipati)

22, *Stagmomantis limbata* adult male copulating with *Mantis religiosa* adult female. Rail Rd Flat, Calaveras Co, CA 09.19.25 (Photo: randy161)

23, *Stagmomantis limbata* adult male copulating with *Mantis religiosa* adult female, eliciting sexual cannibalism. Rosemont, Sacramento Co, CA 09.01.24 (Photo: Mark B)

24, *Stagmomantis limbata* adult males scramble mounting with *Tenodera sinensis* adult female. Walnut Creek, Contra Costa Co, CA 09.26.17 (Photo: Kim Leonard)

25, *Stagmomantis limbata* adult male copulating with *Stagmomantis wheelerii* adult female, eliciting sexual cannibalism. Pima Co, AZ 09.13.12 (Photo: Dan Logen)

Additional observation of adult male *limbata* vs adult female *religiosa*

- Concord, Contra Costa Co, CA (10.09.19) Observation ID: 44265711

Stagmomantis (Nigralora) wheelerii (Thomas, 1875)

Remarks. Heterospecific mounting behavior in *Stagmomantis wheelerii* has been documented under natural field conditions, providing a reciprocal counterpart to previously recorded observations involving a *limbata* male. In this case, an adult male *wheelerii* was observed mounting an adult female *limbata*, the inverse of the documented *limbata* vs *wheelerii* copulation documented earlier. Although *wheelerii* and *limbata* exhibit superficial similarity in size, coloration, and general habitus, the two species represent distinct evolutionary lineages placed in separate subgenera within *Stagmomantis*. Their sympatry in portions of the southwestern United States creates ecological conditions in which opportunistic male mate-search behavior may bring the species into frequent contact. As with most Mantidae exhibiting scramble-based mating systems, the observed interaction involved mounting behavior only, without evidence of genital engagement or terminal flexion. The existence of reciprocal heterospecific interactions between *wheelerii* and *limbata* reinforces that males of both species possess similarly nondiscriminatory initial mate-recognition thresholds and that shared habitat structure provides ample opportunity for such events.

26, *Stagmomantis wheelerii* adult male mounting *Stagmomantis limbata* adult female. San Joaquin Hills, Orange Co, CA 09.27.23 (Photo: Jacob Donaldson)

Stagmomantis (Stagmomantis) carolina (Linné, 1763)

Remarks. Heterospecific mounting behavior in *Stagmomantis carolina* has been documented on several occasions, demonstrating that this species aligns with other Mantidae in its reliance on rapid, visually triggered mate-search strategies that can override species-specific discrimination. One notable observation involved an adult male *carolina* mounting an adult female *Tenodera sinensis*, a species several times larger in overall mass and originating from the Indo-Malaysian region. The extreme size discrepancy, combined with the absence of any shared evolutionary history between these taxa in the Nearctic, underscores the nondiscriminatory nature of male *carolina* mounting responses when encountering similarly mantis-shaped forms. A second instance involved an adult male *carolina* mounting a similarly sized adult female *Tenodera angustipennis*. As with most heterospecific interactions in Mantidae, these events consisted solely of mounting behavior, lacking evidence of terminal flexion or genital engagement. It is interesting to note that female *Tenodera*, in addition to being much larger and more elongated than *carolina* females, are macropterous, whereas *carolina* females have an entirely different habitus and are brachypterous. A third observation recorded an adult male *carolina* attempting copulation with an adult male *Stagmomantis conspurcata*. This homosex, heterospecific interaction reinforces that the initial mounting phase in *carolina* is guided almost entirely by coarse visual cues rather than pheromonal recognition. Together, these records reveal that *carolina* males exhibit broad, opportunistic mating attempts consistent with the sensory and behavioral constraints typical of Mantidae. Heterospecific and homosex mounting events remain non-functional in reproductive terms but provide important evidence of how visual bias, urgency, and low discrimination thresholds can shape mating behavior within this family.

27, *Stagmomantis carolina* adult male mounting *Tenodera sinensis* adult female. Wyndmoor, Montgomery Co, PA 09.26.22

28, *Stagmomantis carolina* adult male mounting *Tenodera angustipennis* adult female. Fountainhead-Orchard Hills, Washington Co, MD 09.10.22 (Photo: Claire Zimmermann)

29, *Stagmomantis carolina* adult male attempting copulation with *Stagmomantis conspurcata* adult male. Dripping Springs, Hays Co, TX 10.09.18 (Photo: Greg Lasley)

Additional observations of adult male *carolina* vs adult female *sinensis*

- Muncie, Delaware Co, IN (09.18.22) Observation ID: 135575938

Additional observations of adult male *carolina* vs adult male *conspurcata*

- Norman, Cleveland Co, OK (09.10.19) Observation ID: 32503382

Stagmomantis (Stagmomantis) resacae Anderson, 2021

Remarks. Heterospecific mounting behavior in *Stagmomantis resacae* is documented from a field observation in which two adult males simultaneously mounted an adult female *Pseudovates chlorophaea*. This event represents a particularly striking case of scramble-competition mating involving a species wholly unrelated to *Stagmomantis*. *Pseudovates chlorophaea* belongs to a separate lineage within Mantidae and exhibits a markedly different habitus compared to *resacae* females. The simultaneous mounting by two males indicates a classic scramble-mating scenario in which urgency and visual triggers override species discrimination entirely. The fact that *resacae* males responded to such an ecologically and morphologically divergent taxon such as *Pseudovates* demonstrates that the early stages of male mate detection and mounting in this species depend on coarse, generalized visual cues rather than species-specific form recognition or pheromonal filtering. This case highlights the extent of sensory and behavioral flexibility in male *resacae* and supports the broader conclusion that male Mantidae often initiate mounting with any encountered figure that falls within a general visual threshold for “potential mate,” even when the target is entirely incompatible in morphology, lineage, and reproductive potential.

30, *Stagmomantis resacae* adult males scramble mounting with *Pseudovates chlorophaea* adult female. Hidalgo, Hidalgo Co, TX 04.17.22 (Photo: Joseph Connors)

Statilia maculata (Thunberg, 1784)

Remarks. A heterospecific mounting event has been documented in *Statilia maculata*, wherein an adult male *maculata* was observed mounting an adult female *Stagmomantis carolina* in an area where the two species are presently sympatric. As with other Mantidae exhibiting visually triggered scramble-competition mating, the male *maculata* showed no discrimination against this unrelated native species. The event consisted of mounting and terminal flexion, suggesting a potential copulation attempt. This observation is significant in demonstrating that *Statilia*, despite being phylogenetically distant from *Stagmomantis*, nonetheless shares the same generalized sensory and behavioral predisposition found across Mantidae males.

31, *Statilia maculata* adult male mounting *Stagmomantis carolina* adult female. Baltimore, Baltimore Co, MD 09.11.21 (Photo: Nicole Hartig)

Tenodera sinensis Saussure, 1871

Remarks. Heterospecific mating behavior in *Tenodera sinensis* is among the most frequently documented for any adventive mantid in the United States, with numerous field observations recording adult male *sinensis* mounting adult female *Mantis religiosa*, including several instances of scramble-competition mating. The prevalence of this interaction is notable given that *sinensis* and *religiosa* originate from entirely separate biogeographic regions (Southeast Asia and the Mediterranean basin, respectively) and share no evolutionary history prior to their introduction into North America. Their sympatry is a direct consequence of independent human-mediated introductions, without which such heterospecific encounters would never have occurred naturally. This particular pairing also reverses the predominant pattern seen in other heterospecific heterosexual mountings within Mantidae, where males are typically one or more orders of magnitude smaller than the mismatched females they attempt to mount. In contrast, *sinensis* males are substantially larger and longer-bodied than *religiosa* females. Despite their superior size and ability to achieve terminal flexion during mounting attempts, none of the documented cases have progressed to successful copulation. The most plausible explanation is mechanical incompatibility: the male *sinensis* body plan, especially the extreme elongation of the abdomen and thorax, appears to prevent the necessary contortion required to achieve genital alignment with the comparatively compact female *religiosa*. Thus, while initial anchoring gestures may be attempted, full genital engagement is unlikely to occur. These repeated but non-functional interactions provide a compelling example of how anthropogenic reshuffling of global faunas facilitates novel and otherwise evolutionarily impossible heterospecific mating interactions within Mantidae.

32, *Tenodera sinensis* adult male mounting *Mantis religiosa* adult female. Brooklyn, Kings Co, NY 09.24.24 (Photo: Matthew Wills)

33, *Tenodera sinensis* adult males scramble mounting with *Mantis religiosa* adult female. Toledo, Lucas Co, OH 09.11.20 (Photo: Rick Nirschl)

Additional observations of adult male *sinensis* vs adult female *religiosa*

- North Wales, Montgomery Co, PA (09.02.22) Observation ID: 136650722
- Burlington, Chittenden Co, VT (10.23.24) Observation ID: 248805275
- Willard, Salt Lake Co, UT (09.10.24) Observation ID: 241021507
- King of Prussia, Montgomery Co, PA (10.02.21) Observation ID: 97212713
- Media, Delaware Co, PA (09.17.21) Observation ID: 95966719
- Cranbury, Middlesex Co, NJ (09.05.21) Observation ID: 93718097
- North Falmouth, Barnstable Co, MA (09.25.20) Observation ID: 60720010
- Seven Hills, Cuyahoga Co, OH (09.16.24) Observation ID: 242181980
- Monclova, Lucas Co, OH (09.16.16) Observation ID: 4127946

Tenodera sinensis welcoming *Statilia maculata* to America... with a complimentary meal plan— proudly protecting its invasive turf.

“You’re new here, right? Let me show you around... my digestive tract.”

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